

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D2.2 Indicator Framework Developed

Work Package	WP2 Verifiable indicator framework & guidelines
Task	T2.1 Coordinate data provision and develop indicator framework
Lead author	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)
Contributors	Siân Astley (EuroFIR AISBL), Christine Absil (Clupea), Michelle Boonstra (Clupea), Tracy Murai (Poseidon), Tim Huntington (Poseidon), Yannis Tzitzikas (FORTH)
Peer reviewers	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish), Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	30/04/2025
Submission Date	30/04/2025

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Version History

Rev.	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	21.01.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	ToC defined
0.2	31.01.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Draft description of sources on Environmental Indicators
0.3	14.02.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Draft description of sources on Nutrition and Health Indicators
0.4	16.03.2025	Cristine Absil (Clupea)	Revision and feedback
0.5	20.03.2025	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Suggestion of new section on Indicator selection
0.6	28.03.2025	Tracy Murai (Poseidon)	Introduction to social and economic indicators
0.7	31.03.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Social and economic indicators sources description
0.8	01.04.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Social and economic indicators sources description
0.9	04.04.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH), Tracy Murai (Poseidon)	Description of more sources on Environmental Indicators Socio-Economic Indicators data sources
0.10	08.04.2025	Tracy Murai (Poseidon)	Socio-Economic Indicators data sources
0.11	09.04.2025	Tim Huntington (Poseidon)	Aquaculture indicators consolidated description
0.12	10.04.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Environmental Indicators data sources refinement
0.13	11.04.2025	Christine Absil (Clupea), Yannis Marketakis (FORTH) Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	Further details on indicators Indicator Matrix General revision and updates
0.14	16.04.2025	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	First internal review
0.15	22.04.2025	Tracy Murai (Poseidon)	Contribution to Socio-economic indicators and general revision of the document
0.16	23.04.2025	Christine Absil	Fisheries details on indicators finalised
0.17	25.04.2025	Yannis Tzitzikas (FORTH)	Revision and comments
0.18	25.04.2025	Siân Astley (EuroFIR AISBL)	Revision and contributions for Nutrition and Health indicators and data sources
0.19	28.04.2025	Christine Absil (Clupea)	Revision and comments
0.20	28.04.2025	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	Revision and comments
1.0	29.04.2025	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)	Final version of the deliverable

Keywords

Sustainability indicators; VeriFish framework; aquafood; environmental impact; nutrition and health.

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafood repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AQ	Farmed Aquafood
ASC	Aquaculture Stewardship Council
BMIS	Bycatch Management Information System
CITES	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CPI	Corruption Perception Index
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
DCF	Data Collection Framework
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ETP	Endangered, Threatened, Protected
EUMOFA	European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
FAD	Fish Aggregating Devices
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FCDB	Food Composition Database
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Programme
FoC	Flag of Convenience

Item	Description
GFCM	General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GNR	Global Nutrition Report
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GSI	Global Slavery Index
GSSI	Global Sustainable SeaFood Initiative
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ILO	International Labour Organization
ISSCFG	FAO International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear
IUU	Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated fishing
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OHS	Occupational Health and Safety
OWI	Operational Welfare Indicators
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rule
PSA	Productivity Susceptibility Analysis
PUFA	Polyunsaturated Fatty Acid
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organizations
SB	Steering Board
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
TI	Transparency Index
TCMF	Technical Conservation Measures Framework
UN	United Nations
WC	Wild-caught Aquafood
WISE-MARINE	Water Information System for Europe - Marine
WG	Working Group
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

VeriFish aims to offer a **comprehensive framework of sustainability indicators**, integrating data from trusted sources to assess environmental, social, and health-related factors in aquafood production, with the ultimate objective of allowing industry professionals and consumers alike to make informed decisions based on **transparent, verifiable data**.

This deliverable follows *D2.1 - Indicator Framework Defined*, which defined a comprehensive suite of indicators that might be used to assess and communicate sustainability in the aquafood sector, focusing on fisheries, aquaculture, and human health.

The indicator framework is built around three pillars, each addressing a critical dimension of sustainability to provide a holistic approach to assessing and communicating sustainability of aquafood. These pillars are: **(a) Environmental, (b) Nutrition, and (c) Social and Economic**, and serve as a backbone for sustainability assessment and communication.

In contrast, this deliverable focuses on: **(a) practical application of these indicators** (Section 2), and **(b) data sources that can be used for implementation of the framework** (Sections 3,4 and 5). More specifically, we catalogue and describe key data sources, detailing their coverage, and relevance, and explain access and processing of these data. Moreover, we map data sources to specific indicators, clarifying how each source contributes to describing sustainability across the different pillars. **A matrix** is also presented that aligns data sources with the indicators in the framework (Section 6). Overall, the final version of the framework comprises 84 indicators distributed across the three main pillars, each further categorized into specific sub-pillars. In addition, more than 35 relevant data sources have been identified and described to support the application and monitoring of these indicators.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction & Background	9
1.1 Indicator Framework Summary	9
1.2 Objectives of the deliverable	10
1.3 Links with other deliverables	11
1.4 Structure of the deliverable	11
2 VeriFish Finalised Indicator Framework	11
2.1 Environmental Indicators	12
2.2 Nutrition and Health Indicators	43
2.3 Social and Economic Indicators	48
3 Environmental Indicators data sources	55
3.1 Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)	57
3.2 FishBase	60
3.3 SeaLifeBase	61
3.4 Sea Around Us	62
3.5 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species & Relevant sources	64
3.6 EMODNET Biology datasets	66
3.7 Data Collection Framework (DCF)	66
3.8 WISE-Marine	67
3.9 European Nature Information System (EUNIS)	67
3.10 Aquafood Rating Schemes (e.g. WWF Common Methodology)	68
3.11 FAIR-FISH-Database	70
3.12 Bycatch Management Information System (BMIS)	71
3.13 FishSource	73
3.14 FisheryProgress	73
3.15 Other relevant sources	73
4 Nutrition and Health Indicators Data Sources	75
4.1 FAO/INFOODS Global Food Composition Database for Fish and Shellfish (uFish)	76
4.2 EuroFIR - FoodEXplorer	77
4.3 FoodEx2	80
4.4 World Health Organization (WHO) data collections	81
4.5 Global Nutrition Report (GNR)	82
5 Social and Economic Indicators Data Sources	83

5.1 ILO Conventions	85
5.2 Global Slavery Index	87
5.3 Transparency International	87
5.4 Data Collection Framework (DCF)	88
5.5 European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products	88
5.6 EMODnet Human Activities	88
5.7 The Trafficking in Persons Report	89
5.8 Official 'IUU' Vessel Lists	90
5.9 Flags of Convenience Lists	91
5.10 Port State Measures Agreement	91
5.11 Subsidies for Fishing Vessels	92
5.12 IMO STCW-F Ratification	93
5.13 The Global Record of Fishing Vessels, Refrigerated Transport Vessels and Supply Vessels (Global Record)	93
5.14 FishStatJ	94
6 Indicator Framework Matrix	94
7 Conclusions	99

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. The final list of environmental indicators taken into consideration in the VeriFish framework...	13
Figure 2 GRSF indicators relating to stock status.....	17
Figure 3. Ratings of habitat and bycatch impacts for each gear class, as determined by participants of a workshop held in March 2002 in Seattle, WA (Morgan and Chuenpagdee 2003).....	18
Figure 4. Calculation of the resulting score for the impact on the seabed indicator (sum of the scores from the fishing gears impact and habitat sensitivity).....	19
Figure 5. Workflow for implementing a sensitive species indicator (STECF EWG 23-18).....	25
Figure 6. Attribute application and scoring for 'Stocking density'.....	36
Figure 7. Attribute application and scoring for 'Greenhouse gas emissions'.....	38
Figure 8. Attribute application and scoring for effluent emissions.....	40
Figure 9. Sample of information about a stock record describing Hake in the Adriatic Sea retrieved from the GRSF.....	57
Figure 10. FishBase public portal.....	58

Figure 11. Example of interactive graph from the Sea Around Us portal.....	61
Figure 12. Geographic range of a critically endangered species from the IUCN Red List.....	63
Figure 13. WWF common methodology for environmental sustainability of seafood species.....	67
Figure 14. Fair-Fish database sample page.....	69
Figure 15. Time series of Green turtle bycatch by the Bycatch Management Information System.....	70
Figure 16. FoodExplorer resources filtered via the EuroFIR portal.....	77
Figure 17. Sample results from GetFoodNutVal on nutritive value of salmon.....	78

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1. Attributes for capture fisheries.....	12
Table 2. Updated capture fisheries indicators with key relevant attributes and data sources for T1 and T2 levels.....	13
Table 3. Attributes for Aquaculture.....	29
Table 4. Updated aquaculture indicators with key relevant attributes and data sources for T1 and T2 levels.....	32
Table 5. highly relevant nutrition and health indicators.....	43
Table 6. medium relevant nutrition and health indicators.....	44
Table 7. low relevant nutrition and health indicators.....	46
Table 8. Social and Economic Indicators.....	47
Table 9. Inventory of environmental indicators data sources.....	54
Table 10. Main nutrition and health data sources considered in the VeriFish framework.....	73
Table 11. Key social and economic data sources considered in the VeriFish framework.....	82
Table 13. Matrix of aquaculture indicators and data sources.....	94
Table 14. Matrix of social and economic indicators and data sources.....	96

1 Introduction & Background

VeriFish aims to simplify and consolidate information about indicators that can be used in the narrative of sustainability for aquafoods. More specifically, the project is developing a framework of verifiable indicators based on reliable data from a wide variety of European and global sources. The indicators were identified, reviewed and selected based on how they might help actors in aquafood chains provide information (e.g. nutrition, environmental, societal) about products, thereby enabling consumers to make more informed decisions at points of purchase. Using white labelled media products and a prototype web application, VeriFish will exemplify how verifiable data can be collated by actors and shared with consumers, ultimately helping to promote more responsible consumption patterns and reward aquafood production striving for improved sustainability.

1.1 Indicator Framework Summary

The VeriFish Indicator Framework (mentioned simply as framework in the remaining of this document) is an innovative and comprehensive system designed to address the growing need for transparent, standardised, and actionable sustainability-related metrics in the aquafood sector. By integrating three foundational pillars - *Environmental*, *Social & Economic*, and *Nutrition & Health* - it aims to provide a robust, multi-dimensional approach to assessing and communicating sustainability by diverse stakeholders, including producers, retailers, policymakers, to consumers. By bridging gaps in data accessibility, communication, and decision-making, the framework aims to offer trustable and verifiable information on sustainable aquafood that indirectly could foster and encourage a more sustainable consumption of aquafood in Europe.

The framework is built on a **tiered data system** to accommodate diverse needs and capacities of aquafood actors. **Tier 1** comprises publicly available data from global or regional or even country-level repositories. These datasets are highly accessible, free (in general), and scientifically validated. These offer broad, high level and less detailed insights disparately but are more comprehensive when consolidated. **Tier 2 data** differs because these sources can be attributed to specific value chains, detailing production methods, practices, and proprietary information. The use of this dual-tier system will enable the framework to balance accessibility with granularity, ensuring that high-level information and detailed assessments can be brought together.

The framework is underpinned by three pillars, each addressing critical dimensions of sustainability with transparency and scientific rigour:

- **ENVIRONMENTAL PILLAR** focuses on minimising ecological harm and promoting sustainable resource use within capture fisheries and aquaculture, leveraging scientifically validated indicators to measure and communicate key aspects, including stock status, climate and ecosystem impacts, and waste and pollution. This pillar emphasises ecological aspects, such as stock availability, species biology, habitats and adaptability, allowing consumers to make more informed decisions that protect aquatic ecosystems while maintaining productivity.

- **SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC PILLAR** highlights the importance of fair and responsible practices in production of aquafood, focusing on people, communities, and governance systems that underpin supply chains. This pillar integrates data on labour rights, working conditions, governance, and economic contributions to provide a clearer picture of social risks and opportunities in both wild-capture and aquaculture systems. It supports users in identifying potential human rights concerns, promoting equitable employment, and recognising the role of aquafood in supporting livelihoods. Key areas of focus include decent work, social inclusion, transparency, and community well-being. This pillar underpins the development of responsible sourcing guidance and enhances the credibility of sustainability claims across the sector
- **NUTRITION AND HEALTH PILLAR** highlights the critical role of aquafood in supporting human health and addressing dietary needs. This pillar integrates data on nutritional composition of aquafood products with environmental and social and economic aspects, enabling actors to understand and communicate health benefits and consumers to make more informed decisions about consumption. Key areas of focus include nutrient quality and dietary impact on health. This pillar supports the development of guidelines emphasising the importance of aquafood in achieving balanced and sustainable diets.

1.2 Objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable stems from the definition of the framework and its details documented in D2.1¹. The current deliverable focuses on identifying the relevant data sources that contribute to the framework, their level of publicity, the methods for accessing and retrieving them and their alignment within the framework. In more details, the key objectives are:

- Identify the relevant data sources that can contribute to the development of the framework, and document their level of publicity (public, private, restricted)
- Define the main entities of interest from each source (i.e. focus on particular aspects of a data source)
- Outline the methods for accessing and collecting information such as APIs, downloadable datasets, etc.
- Explicitly map data sources to the framework, clarifying how each data source contributes to specific indicators.

¹ Astley, S. (2024). VeriFish Indicator Framework defined- D2.1 (1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14384281>

1.3 Links with other deliverables

This deliverable is the direct outcome of the framework established and thoroughly described in *D2.1*, where the main pillars and attributes are described in detail. Furthermore, the contents of the current deliverable provide the required documentation for the contents of the VeriFish Knowledge Base (KB), which will be delivered as *D2.4*. We should also mention that some of the data sources described in the following sections, are already integrated in VeriFish KB. These activities are described in *D2.4 - VeriFish Knowledge Base - interim version*, which is delivered concurrent with *D2.2*. Finally, an enhanced version of VeriFish KB, integrating more data sources will be delivered during the second year of the project on February 2026 (M22) (*D2.5 - VeriFish Knowledge Base - final version*).

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the background information about the framework, and the overall positioning of the current deliverable.
- **Section 2** presents an updated, consolidated and more comprehensive version of the indicators.
- **Section 3** outlines the data sources that are relevant to the environmental indicators.
- **Section 4** outlines the data sources that are relevant to the nutrition and health indicators.
- **Section 5** outlines the data sources that are relevant to the social and economic indicators.
- **Section 6** maps how different data sources contribute to specific indicators.
- **Section 7** concludes with a summary of the findings and identifies implications for future work.

2 VeriFish Finalised Indicator Framework

This section revisits and finalises the list of indicators proposed in *D2.1* by carrying out a consolidated assessment across all three pillars of sustainability. While *D2.1* laid the groundwork by identifying relevant indicators and attributes, here we focus on refining those selections and filling in missing gaps - especially for the social and economic dimension. The goal is to validate and finalise a **consistent set of indicators that can realistically be applied, verified, and used** in the next steps of the project. This includes ensuring each indicator is supported by appropriate data sources and that it reflects the needs of future communication and scoring efforts (e.g. factsheets, the web app, traffic light systems). While environmental and nutrition and health indicators have been more extensively addressed in the literature and supported by relevant data sources, the development of social and economic indicators remains at an early stage. In the current deliverable we made a first identification of the corresponding indicators for the social and economic pillar.

To that end, indicators have been reviewed not only for their technical relevance but also for their usefulness in practice, especially in relation to the upcoming scoring methodology and communication guidelines. Some previously proposed indicators have been dropped where verification proved too difficult or where overlap was found. New indicators have been added where important gaps existed—particularly in the social and economic pillar.

2.1 Environmental Indicators

The indicators and related attributes are further described below, grouped by capture fishery and aquaculture indicators.

2.1.1 Capture Fisheries

The D2.1 report provided an initial assessment of both attributes and provisional indicators of the assessed environmental level of sustainability of products coming from capture fisheries. Both these aspects have been reviewed and refined and the results presented below. Below we describe the main attributes (i.e. the specific characteristics of the indicators), and indicators (i.e. the measurable variables or parameters of a particular aspect) of capture fisheries.

2.1.1.1 Attributes

Table 1. Attributes for capture fisheries

Attribute	Commentary
Species	Accurate species identification is vital, with Latin (scientific) names preferred to avoid confusion caused by regional variations in common names. For fresh aquafood products, Regulation No. 1379/2013 ² mandates the use of scientific names.
Capture method	The gear that was used to capture the aquatic animal. Gears expressed as provided by the FAO International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear (ISSCFG) which categorises fishing equipment into 10 broad groups and 47 gear types (Classification and illustrated definition of fishing gears ³). This is more detailed than legally required under Regulation No. 1379/2013 ⁴ .
Area	The location where fish are caught (be that an ocean, lake, or river) is crucial for a sustainability assessment. Oceanic catch areas are categorised into FAO regions worldwide (e.g., NE Atlantic as FAO 27, Mediterranean as FAO 37) and further divided into smaller GFCM regions (General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean), some designated by ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea), which are mandatory for products caught in European Union waters under Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 ⁵ .

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013R1379>

³ <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/d194ba36-af7a-48ed-9e58-563143b96863/content>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013R1379>

5

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R1308>

2.1.1.2 Capture fisheries indicators

The current, finalised list of environmental indicators for capture fisheries is provided below. They have been organised in **5 sub pillars related to: stock status, ecological impact, climate impact, governance and animal welfare.**

Figure 1. The final list of environmental indicators taken into consideration in the VeriFish framework

Table 2 summarized the updated capture fisheries indicators, with the key relevant attributes (i.e. species, capture method, area) and the data sources that are required for T1 and T2. Subsequently, more details are provided for each indicator.

Table 2. Updated capture fisheries indicators with key relevant attributes and data sources for T1 and T2 levels

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned			T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
			1	2	3		
01	Stock status	Stock status	x		x	GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned			T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
			1	2	3		
02	Fishing mortality	Stock status	x		x	GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level
03	Resilience	Stock status	x			Resilience score from Fishbase	Not applicable at vessel level
04	CO2eq/kg landed catch	Climate impact		x		Typical fuel consumption data per catch method and species	Greenhouse gas emissions of vessel as CO2eq/kg landed product
05	Habitat impact	Ecological impact		x	x	Gear x seabed type proxy. Scoring through association of species with certain habitat	Specific information on fishing location. Related to EUNIS https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eunis-habitat-classification .
06	Trophic effects	Ecological impact		x	x	Biomass data from GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level
07	Bycatch	Ecological impact		x	x	Amount of discard typical for gear type and landed catch	Amount of discard typical for vessel and landed catch
08	Potential bycatch risk of sensitive Species	Ecological impact		x	x	STECF-EWG 23-18 risk assessment methodology, CITES convention, CMS convention, IUCN red list of threatened species.	(Digital) registration of catch of ETP species at vessel level
09	Gear loss	Ecological impact		x	x	Gear based risk	Vessel based mitigation measures or plan

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned			T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
			1	2	3		
10	Capture OWI	Animal welfare	x	x		Generic OWI score for gear operation	OWI Score at vessel level. Or applied extra mitigation measures.
11	Handling OWI	Animal welfare	x	x		Generic OWI score for gear operation	OWI Score at vessel level. Or applied extra mitigation measures.
12	Stunning and Killing	Animal welfare	x	x		Unlikely at generic level. Maybe in future when legally required, then RFMO or region determines	Effective stunner implemented on board yes/no
13	Monitoring plan	Governance	x		x	Level of monitoring. Present, intensity and quality	Not applicable at vessel level
14	Stock assessment	Governance	x		x	Information on HCR, TAC sharing agreement and enforcement	Not applicable at vessel level
15	ETP impact mitigation	Governance		x	x	Mandatory measures by regulation	Use of escape panels, pingers. No or adapted FAD's, active avoidance of aggregations
16	Discards mitigation	Governance		x	x	Mandatory measures by regulation	Use of measures on board
17	Catch limit	Governance	x		x		
18	Regulatory framework	Governance	x		x	On government level	Not applicable at vessel level

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned			T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
			1	2	3		
19	IUU	Governance			x	The Global Record of Fishing Vessels, Refrigerated Transport Vessels and Supply Vessels	Future: digitalised proof of uninterrupted AIS
20	Certification	Governance	x	x	x	Fleet level certification (GSSI/ISEAL benchmarked) or Fishery Improvement Program (FisheryProgress)	Vessel-level certification

Indicators 01 - 02 - 03: Stock status

For the indicators relating to stock status (biomass, fishing mortality, resilience), a lot of the information is available through databases. The GRSF has detailed information, both on biomass levels and fishing mortality, that can be used in a scoring system such as presented by STECF for a basic system (system 1), or a system with more detailed data (system 2)⁶.

⁶ Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) – Validation of selected sustainability indicators and underlying methodologies for the revision of the EU marketing standards for fisheries products (STECF-22-12). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022,

Figure 2 GRSF indicators relating to stock status

Alternatively, stock status scores can be directly derived from FishSource⁷, which assigns scores across various indicators, each focusing on a different aspect of fisheries management. These indicators are scored on a 0–10 scale. For example, the score for stock health measures the SSB as a percentage of the MSY Btrigger. Where no information on either stock or fishing mortality is available, resilience information can be derived from FishBase⁸. In a situation with data deficiency, combined with a low resilience, a species should receive a relatively high-risk score.

Indicator 04 Climate impact

To address the environmental footprint of products, the European Commission is developing product environmental footprint category rules (PEFCR) to standardise calculation and comparisons of environmental impacts across products and services. These rules are comprehensive and consider multiple factors, but they require extensive data, posing challenges for widespread implementation. Also, they only consider marine fish. Crustaceans, molluscs, freshwater fish, and prepared and preserved products are not included. Moreover, these PEFCR do not include biodiversity aspects.

For capture fisheries, climate impact is the most relevant parameter in the Product Environmental Footprint. We therefore suggest limiting this indicator and not use PEFCR. The most suitable metric for assessing climate impact of seafood is CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq) per Kg of product. For Tier 1, the scores are based on fuel use per gear type and fishery. Several databases have data on fuel use in fisheries, for example the Seafood Carbon Emissions Tool⁹.

For Tier 2, more detailed information can be calculated through the Climate Impact Tool that is currently being developed by the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) and this will be publicly available. A similar tool is also being developed on aquaculture by the ASC.

Indicator 05 Ecological Impact [Habitat impact]

It is well known that some fishing gears have impacts on marine habitats, these impacts can be more severe if the habitat is highly productive or particularly fragile. The extent of the impacts depends on various factors, including the type and scale of the habitat, the fishing method used, and the interaction between fishing activities and ecosystem components.

This concept usually is typically applied to benthic habitats, but it should also be extended to the pelagic environment, where important ecological dynamics in the water column may be overlooked. However, due to a lack of scientific consensus on how to assess the impacts of fishing on pelagic habitats, the current focus remains on benthic habitats as a first step.

⁷ <https://sustainablefish.org/tools-science-services/fishsource/>

⁸ <https://fishbase.org/>

⁹ <http://seafoodco2.dal.ca/>

Building on work by the STECF, Grati *et al*¹⁰ proposed a scoring approach based on associating the gear type to a given impact on benthic marine habitats. The impact of fishing gears on the physical structure of habitats of the seafloor was first categorised using a simple method based on levels (high, medium, low) following a simplified version of the procedure reported in Morgan and Chuenpagdee (2003)¹¹.

Gear class	Habitat		Bycatch				
	Physical	Biological	Shellfish & crabs	Finfish	Sharks	Marine mammals	Sea birds & turtles
Dredges	5	5	4	2	1	1	1
Gillnet - bottom	3	2	1	4	3	4	3
Gillnet - midwater	1	1	1	4	4	5	5
Hook and line	1	1	1	2	3	1	2
Longline - bottom	2	2	1	4	3	1	2
Longline - pelagic	1	1	1	3	4	3	5
Pots & traps	3	2	4	2	1	3	1
Purse seine	1	1	1	2	2	3	2
Trawl - bottom	5	5	3	5	2	2	2
Trawl - midwater	1	1	1	3	2	2	2

1 Very low
 2 Low
 3 Medium
 4 High
 5 Very high

Figure 3. Ratings of habitat and bycatch impacts for each gear class, as determined by participants of a workshop held in March 2002 in Seattle, WA (Morgan and Chuenpagdee 2003)

The second step was to account for the sensitivity of specific marine habitats to each particular fishing gear in the scoring, keeping in mind that detailed fishing location is not available in the CMO data and spatial habitat information cannot thus be used directly. To achieve this, Grati *et al* thus used the **species information** as a surrogate, linking a species with its “typical habitat”. Marine habitats and commercial marine organisms (e.g., fishes, molluscs, crustaceans, etc.) preferential habitats data were issued from

¹⁰ Fabio Grati, Jean-Noël Druon, Didier Gascuel, Christine Absil, François Bastardie, Sara Bonanomi, Gianna Fabi, Gildas Glemarec, Jerome Guitton, Sara Hornborg, Ane Iriondo, Armelle Jung, Stefanos Kalogirou, Daniel Li Veli, Josep Lloret, Christos Maravelias, Dimitrios K. Moutopoulos, Tiit Raid, Anna Rindorf, Antonello Sala, Martina Scanu, Giuseppe Scarcella, Vjekoslav Tičina, Clara Ulrich, Alessandro Lucchetti, Fisheries performance indicators for assessing the ecological sustainability of wild-caught seafood products in Europe, Environmental and Sustainability Indicators, Volume 26, 2025, 100632, ISSN 2665-9727, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indic.2025.100632>

¹¹ Ratana Chuenpagdee, Lance E. Morgan, Sara M. Maxwell, Elliott A. Norse and Daniel Pauly (2003). Shifting Gears: Assessing Collateral Impacts of Fishing Methods in US Waters. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* Vol. 1, No. 10, pp. 517-524

various sources such as fishbase.org, sealifebase.org, scientific literature, and technical reports (details in STECF, 2023¹²). Similar to the criteria used for assessing the potential impact of fishing gears on the seabed, the sensitivity of marine habitats to gear action was also categorised into three levels (low, medium, high). In addition, water depth-related terms were assigned to each habitat.

The score of the seabed impact indicator for the fishery product (ranging from 1 to 6) was obtained adding the score of the impact of the fishing gears (ranging from 0 to 3) with the proxy habitat sensitivity score of the target species (ranging from 1 to 3) as illustrated in Figure 4.

		Fishing gear impact			
		0	1	2	3
Habitat sensitivity	1	Very low	Very low	Low	Medium
	2	Very low	Low	Medium	High
	3	Low	Medium	High	Very high

Figure 4. Calculation of the resulting score for the impact on the seabed indicator (sum of the scores from the fishing gears impact and habitat sensitivity)

The system as suggested by Grati *et al* has been put in a provisional app by DG MARE. The first test version of this app (Feb 2025) appeared to have various limitations. Nevertheless, the methodology is a first step. By using the GRSF as a data source for the framework, detailed information on habitats, species and gears is available, potentially allowing for a more refined and truthful outcome of habitat score.

In a tier 2 system, fisheries could have the option to specify, in a reliable and verifiable manner, where exactly the fish species was caught. This information could be overlaid with EMODnet maps using the EUNIS habitat classification system¹³.

¹² Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF), 2023. Validation of Selected Sustainability Indicators and Underlying Methodologies for the Revision of the EU Marketing Standards for Fisheries Products (STECF-22-12). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

¹³ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eunis-habitat-classification>

Such an expert system could be developed by a specialized team, guided by the principles outlined in Morgan and Chuenpagdee (2003). The impact scores—by gear, habitat, and potentially by target species—would be reviewed and validated by a network of scientists selected for their expertise in fishing gear technologies and their knowledge of gear-related habitat impacts.

Indicator 06 Ecological Impact [Trophic effects]

No new information compared to the originally described indicator from D2.1.

Indicator 07 Ecological Impact [Bycatch]

Catch in a fishery is generally divided into targeted catch and bycatch. Bycatch can include both wanted and unwanted species. Wanted bycatch typically refers to species that are not the primary target but that can still be legally landed and sold/used. Unwanted bycatch, on the other hand, includes undersized individuals of commercial species, low value species which are often discarded, or non-commercial species with no market value.

When no reliable data on bycatch and/or discards are available, a risk-based assessment can be completed based on the gear type and the species.

For the indicator bycatch, the best information sources are actual bycatch monitoring programs. These assess the volume and type of bycatch. Reliable monitoring programs are carried out by independent observers, with sufficient coverage of the fleet both spatially and temporally. An alternative for independent observers can be the use of Remote Electronic Monitoring.

Some fisheries have escape panels to allow non-wanted catch to escape. These panels may also cause loss of wanted catch. Effective control and enforcement of gear regulations therefore is essential to determine actual discard rates. In Tier 2 assessments this type of information can be provided.

Fishing gear categories

To allow for a more meaningful classification of fishing gear types, the STECF (STECF 20- identified 12 categories, going beyond the 7 which are mandatory in the EU CMO regulation. The STECF categories include: seines, bottom trawls, pelagic trawls, set nets, driftnets, purse seines, hooks and lines, set longlines, drifting longlines, dredges, pots and traps, and hand implements. The CMO 7 gear categories are considered too broad to differentiate between risks such as bycatch rates or habitat impacts. For example, pelagic trawling poses different risks compared to demersal (bottom) trawling; demersal trawling typically involves mixed-species fisheries, while pelagic trawling usually targets single species schools, leading to different ecological and bycatch profiles.

Yet, also the 12 categories were considered insufficiently detailed by the STECF EWG 23-18 to properly represent the bycatch risk diversity for the full set of species marketed in the EU. Therefore, the EWG 23-18 suggested using more detailed information on corresponding gears and codes (28 gears, plus 4 gears added by the EWG 23-18 for a total of 32 gear categories). Including these gears would however require a revision of the CMO regulation by increasing the mandatory level of details on gear categories.

The EWG 23-18 also noted that, in the specific case of purse seine fisheries, the bycatch indicator for sensitive species would become significantly more meaningful if it would be differentiated between seines targeting small pelagic species, those targeting free-swimming schools of tuna and tuna-like species, and those using Fish Aggregating Devices (FADs). The latter method is associated with a considerably higher risk of bycatch of sensitive species, including the potential for ghost fishing when FADs are lost and left drifting at sea. However, implementing this distinction would require a mechanism to provide verifiable information on the use of FADs—data that is not currently mandated under the CMO regulation.

The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) utilises standardised fishing gear classifications to ensure consistency and interoperability across diverse data sources. Specifically, GRSF adopts the FAO's International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear (ISSCFG) as its primary framework. Additionally, it incorporates the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership (SFP) fishing gear classification, which is mapped to the ISSCFG within the GRSF knowledge base.

The ISSCFG system categorises fishing gear based on operational characteristics, such as how the gear is deployed and retrieved, and the nature of its interaction with target species. This classification encompasses various gear types, including; trawls (e.g. bottom trawls, pelagic trawls), seines (e.g. purse seines, beach seines), gillnets and entangling nets, hooks and lines (e.g. longlines, handlines), lift nets, falling gear (e.g. cast nets), stow nets, traps and pots, dredges, and harpoons and spear guns, and miscellaneous gear (e.g. pumps, explosives). By employing the ISSCFG, the GRSF ensures that gear types are consistently classified, facilitating accurate assessments of fishing practices, their environmental impacts, and aiding in the development of sustainable fisheries management strategies.

In case no information can be derived from the various data sources, The FAO report by Kelleher (2015)¹⁴ provides an overview of discard estimates on a fishery by fishery approach.

Indicator 09 Ecological Impact [Potential bycatch risk of sensitive Species]

Over the past decades, growing public awareness around environmental health has led to a sharp decline in societal tolerance for unsustainable practices, especially when emblematic species are affected. As a result, the incidental catch of Endangered, Threatened, Protected (ETP) and sensitive species is not only an ecological concern but also a matter of strong public expectation. Addressing this issue is essential in defining a sustainable fishery.

The incidental capture of ETP and other sensitive species is considered to pose a major challenge to the conservation of marine biodiversity. Bycatch of these species can have unforeseen consequences on the functioning and resilience of marine ecosystems and vulnerability of the species to other threatening factors e.g. climate change. It primarily concerns marine mammals, seabirds, sea turtles, many species of rays and sharks, and certain finfish species.

¹⁴ Kelleher, Kieran. (2005). Discards in the World's Marine Fisheries. An Update. FAO Fisheries Technical Paper. 470.

Protecting ETP and sensitive species is a fundamental requirement under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which aligns closely with European environmental legislation. This includes the Birds and Habitats Directives, as well as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), all of which are implemented through the Technical Conservation Measures Framework (TCMF). Beyond the TCMF, additional technical measures are enacted through Commission acts and stand-alone regulations. These include rules targeting specific issues such as cetacean bycatch and shark finning onboard vessels. Outside the EU, protection of ETP species is dependent on local legislation. In many regions, the level of protection is not as well regulated as in the EU.

Definitions

To obtain an evaluation or score of the impact on Endangered, Threatened and Protected (ETP) species, it is necessary to first define this category. For reasons of consistency with STECF, this category includes ‘sensitive species’ STECF (EWG 23-18, 2023).

In this report, ETP species are defined as *Endangered*, *Threatened*, and *Protected* species in accordance with IUCN criteria:

- **Endangered:** Species or taxa whose populations have been drastically reduced to critical levels, or whose habitats have been so severely degraded that they are considered at risk of extinction in the short or medium term. This category also includes species that are, in all likelihood, already extinct—those that have not been observed in the wild for the past 50 years.
- **Threatened:** Species facing a significant risk of extinction, based on factors such as population dynamics, biological characteristics (e.g., body size, trophic level, life cycle, breeding behavior, or social structure), and vulnerability related to their tendency to aggregate or to natural fluctuations in population size over time and magnitude, as defined by the IUCN.
- **Protected:** Refers broadly to any species that has been granted legal protection by a *national government*. Most protected species fall into either the threatened or endangered categories. This definition also includes species listed under regional or international agreements, which recognize their declining populations in the wild due to human or other impacts. One of the most stringent international protections is provided by **CITES**, an agreement ratified by nearly all countries, giving listed species a unique and legally binding status. Other international conventions, whether binding or not, ratified by EU Member States or the countries of origin of a product, should also be taken into consideration. The listing of any species at the national or regional level is a clear indication of the need for heightened attention and protection.

Sensitive species are defined as those whose conservation status -including habitat, distribution, population size, or condition - is negatively impacted by pressures resulting from human activities, including fishing. In European waters, this category includes species listed in Annexes II and IV of Directive 92/43/EEC, those covered by Directive 2009/147/EC, and species requiring protection to achieve good environmental status under Directive 2008/56/EC.

It is likely that in some non-European waters or countries similar legislation exists regarding sensitive species. To what extent this is available from databases is unknown.

Assessing sensitivity

When data on stock or fishing effort is limited or not available, the approach of assessing the resilience of the species to fishing pressure can be applied. This information is available in FISHBASE. Alternatively, a more elaborate risk assessment tool for a fishery is an approach called a Productivity Susceptibility Analysis (PSA). This helps managers and scientists identify which species or stocks might be at higher risk of overfishing and those which may need more precautionary management and conservation measures to be implemented and enforced. It also can be used to assess the sensitivity of species in the bycatch indicator.

A PSA combines productivity and susceptibility.

- **Productivity** refers to a species' ability to recover from fishing pressure. It's based on biological traits like growth rate, age at maturity, reproductive rate (fecundity), lifespan and natural mortality rate. Low productivity gives higher vulnerability, because the species recovers slowly. These data are available from FishBase.
- **Susceptibility** refers to how likely the species is to be caught or impacted by a fishery. It considers indicators like overlap with the fishery, gear selectivity, availability, post-capture mortality. High susceptibility means higher risk, because it's more likely to be impacted.

Scoring

In line with the recommendation STECF EWG 23-18, the indicator is now named "Potential bycatch risk of sensitive species" rather than 'impact on sensitive species'. This indicator is intended to assign a risk score based on the likelihood that certain groups of sensitive species are exposed to bycatch.

It is important to note that this definition does *not* represent the population-level risk of depletion caused by the harvesting of sensitive species—an impact which, in most cases, remains unknown.

Scoring approach

Theoretically, when the occurrence of ETP species in an area is known, the combination of information on gear type used, and fishing area, should enable it to generate a risk score on interactions with ETP species for a fishery. Data can be derived from risk based approaches such as vulnerability of cetaceans to impacts from fisheries bycatch¹⁵.

¹⁵ Brown, S.L., Reid, D., and Rogan, E., 2013: A risk-based approach to rapidly screen vulnerability of cetaceans to impacts from fisheries bycatch. *Biological Conservation* 168 (2013) 78-87.

However, deriving a meaningful and scientifically robust indicator from the mandatory information currently available under the CMO regulation is not feasible. The gear categories can be considered to be too broad (for example, there is no distinction in the category trawl: pelagic or demersal), and the FAO fishing area is also broad. This aggregation lacks the required resolution to provide a valid or informative scoring for the intended purpose of the indicator.

The STECF EWG 23-18 (STECF, 2023) faced this problem as well and has tried to develop a consistent scoring system for both EU and imported fishery products. This assessment is derived from the potential overlap between these species and fishing activities in various areas, using available literature on bycatch rates, existing risk assessments, and general knowledge about gear selectivity and post-capture mortality.

The STECF EWG 23-18 decided to base the assessment on information derived from national databases or reports, scientific publications, and various forms of grey literature. By the number of scientific records (qualitative, semi-quantitative and quantitative, mainly scientific papers) identified at FAO area level, the WG could establish a risk score of sensitive species bycatch per FAO fishing area and species group.

Implementation of a sensitive species indicator.

The EWG 23-18 recommended an implementation in 6 steps, the last step being an operational update:

- Step 1: (pre-)database prepared by the EWG 23-18 (12/2023),
- Step 2: Pre-database filling by further ad hoc (dedicated scientific group of experts in bycatch assessments) and/or STECF EWG,
- Step 3: A beta-version of the database is proposed to the stakeholders on a permanent platform (to be decided),
- Step 4: the database is filled by the dedicated scientific group after analysing the existing peer reviewed scientific bycatch information received from the stakeholders in step 3 - the analysis of new scientific bycatch information by the scientific group can take place in parallel,
- Step 5: first operational and publicly available database used to score the products for the bycatch risk of sensitive species (with merging with the other indicators) - kept separate to prepare the next update of the scoring system,
- Step 6: after a fixed period (e.g. 5 years) or substantial changes in the database or continuously depending on practical feasibility, the operational database will be updated, keeping in mind that a too low frequency of update may represent an obstacle to rapid implementation of the best practices of bycatch reduction.

Figure 5. Workflow for implementing a sensitive species indicator (STECF EWG 23-18)

Alternatively, The ratings system of habitat and bycatch impacts by Morgan and Chuenpagdee (2003)¹⁶ could be used as a simplified method to identify bycatch risk for sensitive species.

Indicator 09 Ecological Impact [Gear loss]

In line with STECF definitions, this indicator includes information on plastic waste and pollution. In practice, the main data information sources will be on gear loss. Also the risk of losing Fish Aggregating Devices (FADs) is included in this indicator. STECF suggests for Tier 1 a Risk Based Approach by pseudo-meter. For Tier 2, measures taken by a vessel such as the use of biodegradable escape panels, having a waste mitigation plan in place, or having lost gear retrieval devices installed can be used. Taking part in the Global Ghost Gear Initiative could also be scored. Measures that are taken to reduce the impact of Fish Aggregating Devices can also be included, such as the use of biodegradable materials, or non-entangling FAD design, equipping FADs with GPS and ID codes to monitor and retrieve lost devices.

Indicators 10 -11 - 12 Animal welfare

Animal welfare is a topic in capture fisheries that is always under some scrutiny and that is of consideration for the sector. Even though there is a considerable amount of research on this is being undertaken and the number of industry initiatives to improve the welfare of animals during the fishing process are increasing, there are currently no established, industry-wide welfare indicators in operation.

¹⁶ Ratana Chuenpagdee, Lance E. Morgan, Sara M. Maxwell, Elliott A. Norse and Daniel Pauly (2003). Shifting Gears: Assessing Collateral Impacts of Fishing Methods in US Waters. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* Vol. 1, No. 10, pp. 517-524

Currently these indicators are being developed and might become available for certain species in the coming years.

Indicators 13 - 14- 15 - 16 - 17 - 18 - 19 - 20 Governance

The indicators monitoring plan, stock management plan, measures on mitigating impact on ETP species, measures to minimize discards and measures to reduce impact on the environment can be captured into one meta-indicator ‘management effectiveness’. Management effectiveness is difficult to score as it is very much dependent on the origin of the product, and the level of detail that is known.

STECF suggests for System 1 Risk Based Assessments using a scoring of the Regional Fisheries Management Organisation performances. In the VeriFish Tier 1 level, this can be applied as well. Possibly, through the GRSF, more advanced management information is available. In case the FishSource management scores can be used, this might be a useful data platform.

FishSource is a platform developed by Sustainable Fisheries Partnership (SFP) that provides information on the sustainability of fisheries around the world. One of the key components of FishSource profiles is the Management Score Indicators.

FishSource assigns management scores across five key indicators, each focusing on a different aspect of fisheries management. These indicators are scored on a 0–10 scale. Management Score Indicators 1 and 2 are in the VeriFish framework under Subpillar Stock Status. Management Score Indicators 3-4-5 could be used for the Subpillar Governance.

The five FishSource Management Score Indicators:

1. **Status of the Target Stock**
Measures whether the stock is overfished or subject to overfishing. Considers scientific assessments and biomass levels.
2. **Fishing Mortality**
Evaluates whether fishing pressure is in line with sustainable levels. Looks at catch limits, effort controls, and enforcement effectiveness.
3. **Quality of Management**
Assesses the robustness of the management system. Considers the presence of harvest control rules, compliance, monitoring, and scientific advice use.
4. **Compliance and Enforcement**
Reflects the degree to which regulations are enforced and followed.
Includes monitoring, reporting, and enforcement mechanisms.
5. **Management of Other Impacts (Ecosystem Effects)**
How well does the fishery manage impacts on non-target species and habitats.

It evaluates bycatch management, habitat protection, and ecosystem-based approaches.

Indicator 19: The risk of illegal, or unreported (IUU) fish.

Depending on the data source that is being used in the management effectiveness indicators, a separate indicator to assess the risk level of IUU fish can be used. In a situation of a very data deficient fishery, this indicator might provide information that is otherwise not available.

It makes sense to integrate this indicator with the **social and economic pillar**, since the risk of forced labour is considered to be higher in an illegal fishing operation. Data sources such as the IUU vessel list or the Flags Of Convenience list relevant for the social and economic indicators are also relevant for the indicator on IUU fisheries.

Indicator 20 : Certification

If a fishery undergoes the process of becoming certified by a recognised independent certification scheme that has environmental criteria it can use this certificate as a way to demonstrate that the fishery is environmentally sustainable. Moreover, certification schemes typically also provide *Chain of Custody* control, by way of an additional assessment process, allowing catch that has been certified to be identifiable throughout the entire supply chain.

To assess the quality of certification schemes, it is relevant that a scheme adheres to a set of internationally recognized best practices for sustainability standards. Two major relevant **benchmarks** are the ISEAL Alliance¹⁷ and the Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI)¹⁸.

The ISEAL Alliance is the global membership association for sustainability standards, and its Codes of Good Practice are a set of guidelines that ensure certification schemes are robust, transparent, and credible. Being ISEAL *Code compliant* helps demonstrate that a certification scheme is legitimate, transparent, and committed to achieving meaningful sustainability outcomes. It is an assurance to both producers and consumers that the certified product or service has been evaluated according to rigorous, fair, and credible standards.

ISEAL provides a framework of best practices through its Codes of Good Practice¹⁹, which guide certification schemes to be credible, transparent, and effective.

¹⁷ <https://isealalliance.org/>

¹⁸ <https://ourgssi.org/benchmarking/>

¹⁹

https://isealalliance.org/what-we-do/credible-practice/iseal-code-good-practice-sustainability-systems?gad_source=1&gbraid=0AAAAAplOm1ofGEVTWnh4JvJyWkcjF0XjS&gclid=Cj0KCCQjw2ZfABhDBARIsAHFTxGwwic1EsNXG3gY-2YIFoyq_xCxdyE07Y89Mw3yWSdDZTROqBV0ANKlaAkNHEALw_wcB

The **Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI)** benchmark²⁰ is specifically focused on sustainable seafood certification. GSSI's role is to benchmark and recognize credible, existing seafood certification schemes, ensuring they meet a set of globally accepted sustainability criteria.

ISEAL helps ensure the quality and integrity of certification systems globally across multiple industries, while **GSSI** works to streamline and harmonize the certification process within the seafood industry specifically. Both organizations play complementary roles in ensuring sustainability certifications are credible and effective, but they focus on different aspects of the certification landscape.

The Marine Stewardship Council (MSC)²¹ is both ISEAL compliant and GSSI recognised. It is widely considered the leading fisheries certification scheme. Main reasons are the credibility and robustness of its science-based approach. It is the most widely used ecolabel for wild capture fisheries and covers hundreds of certified fisheries across all continents and oceans.

The MSC has major market influence and buyer trust. Retailers and food service companies use MSC to source responsibly. Many public and private seafood procurement policies require MSC certification or equivalent.

Fisheries Improvement Programmes (FIPs)

Fisheries that are not certified may voluntarily choose to work towards certification [or equivalent standards] through a fisheries improvement programme (FIP). FIPs may be initiated by various organisations or initiatives. The SFP pioneered the use of FIPs to address environmental challenges in marine fisheries. SFP evaluates [FIPs] through the FIP Evaluation Program. The FIP Evaluation Tool²² defines and assesses FIPs against six stages of achievement, including development of the FIP structure (Stages 1 and 2), implementation (Stage 3), improvements (Stages 4 and 5), and MSC certification (Stage 6). Each FIP receives a rating, ranging from an "A" grade of Exceptional Progress to an "E" grade of Negligible Progress.

SFP's progress ratings is the lead metric on FisheryProgress.org²³, the 'one-stop shop' for information on the progress of global FIPs. It makes tracking progress more efficient, consistent, and reliable for businesses that support fishery improvement projects. Ratings for all public FIPs that SFP is aware of are maintained and displayed in the FIPs section for all FishSource profiles that are linked to fishery improvement projects.

²⁰ <https://ourgssi.org/benchmarking/>

²¹ <https://www.msc.org/>

²² https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-uDxBtDRNAcl_ELuPpW-EBjY3M8YB4Dm/view?usp=sharing

²³ <https://fisheryprogress.org/>

2.1.2 Aquaculture

The D2.1 report provided an initial assessment of both attributes and provisional indicators for the environmental sustainability of products coming from aquaculture. Both these aspects have been reviewed and refined and the results presented below.

2.1.2.1 Attributes

The attributes remain broadly the same as follows:

Table 3. Attributes for Aquaculture

Attribute	Commentary
Species	The species of the cultivated plant or animal, at least to genus level. The species will dictate a number of other attributes e.g. feeding level.
Feeding level	Has been simplified (see below), ranging from low trophic, non-fed, extractive species such as shellfish and algae to high trophic carnivorous species. This has a link to many environmental performance issues such as water use, nutrient emissions, greenhouse gas (GHG) contribution, etc.
Production system	The production system used, especially for the longer grow-out period. The key environmental consequence is the 'openness' of the system, which affects issues such as the ability to escape and its consequences, as well as the potential impact of nutrient emissions.
Production cycle status	Includes (i) <i>full cycle</i> (i.e. has been hatchery-bred and grown to final harvest), (ii) <i>restocking</i> (i.e. hatchery-bred and grown for release into the wild as a stock enhancement exercise - also called ranching); or (iii) <i>grow-out only</i> (i.e. juveniles are caught in the wild and then grown out to final harvest in captivity).
Environment	Divided into (i) <i>marine water</i> (e.g. full seawater above 30 parts per thousand (‰)), (ii) <i>brackish water</i> (e.g. 0.5 – 30 ‰) or (iii) <i>fresh water</i> (e.g. less than 0.5 ‰).
Alien status	Whether the whether the species being reared is (i) <i>endemic</i> (e.g. the species is naturally distributed in the location of the aquaculture operation) or (ii) <i>introduced</i> (e.g. the species has been anthropogenically introduced to the location of the aquaculture operation).

The only significant main change has been on the **feeding levels**, where we have moved from the FAO approach²⁴ to one more in line with the approach used by Ziegler *et al* in STECF (2023)²⁵. In this we have categorised feeding levels as follows:

- **Non-fed & extractive:** no feed inputs during the main grow-out phase. This includes low trophic species that are considered as extractive, as they remove nutrients and particulate matter from the environment and metabolise it into biomass. This includes macroalgae and filter-feeding invertebrates.
- **Non-fed - not extractive:** also no feed inputs during the main grow-out phase. These species are not extractive, in that they rely on primary production e.g. phytoplankton and zooplankton, as well as other naturally occurring food matter for their growth. An example might be extensive carp farming in ponds, often in polyculture, where no supplementary feed is provided.
- **Fed – herbivorous:** the stock is provided additional feed inputs during the main grow-out phase. However this does not include any animal protein (marine or terrestrial). An example might be semi-intensive carp farming in ponds, often in monoculture, where supplementary feed is essential for growth.
- **Fed - inc. animal protein:** the stock is provided additional feed inputs during the main grow-out phase. Usually associated with higher trophic, carnivorous species where some inclusion of animal protein (marine or terrestrial) is key for good growth. Examples include intensive salmonid, sea bass, sea bream, catfish and shrimp farming.

Extractive species have a strong environmental performance as not only do they have low nutrient emissions or energy costs associated with their cultivation, they can also provide ecosystem services in terms of removing excessive nutrients and / or capturing and sequestering carbon. As one increases feeding levels there is usually an increase in the trophic level, the scale and nature nutrient emissions and the carbon footprint of production. For example, carnivorous species require marine protein that is usually obtained from geographically distant fisheries and that requires energy-intensive reduction to fishmeal, with aquafeed production contributing to the majority of the carbon footprint of carnivorous fish aquaculture. This is well recognised and for this and economic reasons there have been successful attempts to partially substitute marine proteins with novel alternatives. However, these often have their own environmental concerns and 100% substitution is rarely acceptable.

2.1.2.2 Aquaculture indicators

Following review of the 21 aquaculture environmental indicators proposed in the D2.1 report, seven have been dropped (either because they are difficult to verify, were considered of low relevance or were

²⁴ Baluyut, E. (1989) *Aquaculture Systems and Practices: A Selected Review*. ADCP/REP/89/43. FAO, Rome

²⁵ Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) – *Marketing standards: review of proposed sustainability criteria / indicators for aquaculture (STECF-22-13)*. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/93710, JRC132139.

duplicitous), so 14 now remain. These can be found in Table 2 overleaf and have been re-examined in the following light:

- **Key attributes to be assigned:** examines which of the six identified attributes are potentially relevant to the characterisation and scoring of each indicators.
- **Tier 1 and Tier 2 data needs / sources: an indication for the** type and source of data for the Tier 1 and Tier 2 indicators. Please note these are preliminary, although have been developed in the three examples below.

Three examples of how the attributes will be assessed and used to rank the environmental sustainability of aquaculture products (up to farm gate) have been developed. These are examined below.

1. Maximum stocking density

The maximum stocking density (in either kg/m³ or the number of individuals per m²) is a useful indicator of stock welfare. Exceeding stocking density norms results in additional stress that has multiple impacts on growth, disease resistance and fish quality.

The process for ranking the maximum stocking density against established norms is shown in Figure 6. This shows that both species and production system type are key attributes involved and are usually known and categorised within our attribute lists.

Once the species / production system has been determined, this can be linked to established norms. It is suggested that two main data sources exist:

1. The EU implementing regulation on the production of organic products (EU, 2020²⁶), that provides maximum stocking densities for a wide range of finfish and shellfish species in different production systems in both marine and freshwaters.
2. The recent ‘Good husbandry practices for aquaculture’ (Alvera *et al*, 2024²⁷). This document provides a non-exhaustive list of general and species-specific good husbandry practices (GHPs), including maximum stocking densities in the different production techniques of some of the main European aquaculture species, notably common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*), and mussels (*Mytilus spp.*). In addition are two species of cleaner fish, ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) and lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*). A revised version is currently adding meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*), Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) and turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*).

²⁶ EU (2020). Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/464 of 26 March 2020 laying down certain rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the documents needed for the retroactive recognition of periods for the purpose of conversion, the production of organic products and information to be provided by Member States. C/2020/1772. http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2020/464/oj

²⁷ Alevra, A., Llorente Manzanares, M., Mente, E., Xandri Royo, P.M., (2024). Good husbandry practices for aquaculture, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, doi: 10.2926/1713439

Rows in **bold** are examined in more detail in the following text.

Table 4. Updated aquaculture indicators with key relevant attributes and data sources for T1 and T2 levels

Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned ²⁸						T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Stunning (Y / N / na)	Animal welfare	x			x			Required / not required by national legislation:	Producer policy and practices / methods (dropdown percussive, electric, other)
Maximum stocking density (kg/m³)	Animal welfare	x		x	x			Published statistics for key species / system combinations. The EU has stocking density norms for 8 commonly farmed fin & shellfish species (Alevra <i>et al</i>, 2024) and developing 3 more (meagre, turbot & sole). Stocking density limits are also defined in EU organic production rules ((EU, 2020).	Producer records, probably on an annual basis. Historical stocking density data based on farm records and validated through stocking, harvesting and other production records.

²⁸ 1. Species; 2. Feeding level; 3. Production system; 4. Production cycle status; 5. Environment; 6. Alien status

Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned ²⁸						T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
GHG potential e.g. kg CO ² /tonne production	Climate impact	x	x	x	x	x		Score based on attribute scoring. Will need to be developed and scoring system finalised.	Robust Marine Fish Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) assessment using standardised methodologies e.g. PEF Category Rules (Anon, 2025). The UK's Seafish 'Seafood Carbon Emissions Profiling Tool' could also be used.
Habitat alteration for site (Y / N / na)	Habitat impact			x	x	X		Farm situated in a protected area	Significant habitat alteration that would require a formal restoration / decommissioning plan.
Escapee potential (% / na)	Impact on marine food webs	x		x	x	x	x	Generated by standard aqua variables e.g. open/closed, land-based / open water, native / exotic / introduced, species	Producer records, probably on an annual basis or management measures
Freshwater use (Y/N or m ³ / tonne production)	Resource use	x		x	x	x		Open freshwater system (Y/N)	If yes, m ³ / water per tonne production.

Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned ²⁸						T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Food conversion ratio ((kg growth per kg fed)	Resource use	x	x	x	x			Fed species (Y / N)	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
Effluents released externally	Waste & pollution	x	x	x	x			Score based on attribute scoring. Will need to be developed and scoring system finalised.	Robust Marine Fish Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) assessment using standardised methodologies e.g. PEF Category Rules (Anon, 2025).
Survival rate (%). Over grow-out to harvest	Animal welfare	x		x	x			Published statistics for key species / system combinations, probably at national level.	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
Eye stalk ablation used (Y/N/na)	Animal welfare	x			x			Not possible to score at T1	Producer policy and practices.
Antimicrobial therapeutic treatments used (y / n / na)	Biosecurity	x	x	x	x	x		Available statistics by country on use per species and production system.	Producer records, probably on an annual basis, e.g. when used, how much and why.
Use of GMO feed materials (Y / N / na)	Biosecurity	x	x		x			Permitted / not permitted by national legislation	Producer records, probably on an annual basis. If yes, then

Indicator	Sub-pillar	Key attributes to be assigned ²⁸						T1 data needs / sources	T2 data needs / sources
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
									dropdown of material type and source
Robust EIA required (Y / N / na)	Governance	x	x	x	x	x	X	Required / not required by national legislation	Robust EIA is publicly available
Circularity: proportion plastics reused / recycled (%)	Waste & pollution			x	x	x		National-level compliance with relevant international legislation e.g. EPR, SUP, PRF. (Y/N)	Single-use plastics & multi-use plastics: Weight purchased as a proportion of weight responsibly reused or recycled on an annual basis.

Figure 6. Attribute application and scoring for 'Stocking density'

Based on these two information sources, a Tier 1 ranking may be possible to develop. This ranking will need to be developed into a scoring system that will reflect the known stocking densities against the acceptable norms. If ranking at the Tier 1 level is not possible, the comparison of actual stocking densities (e.g. from historical stocking density data based on farm records and validated through stocking, harvesting and other production records) against established norms should allow Tier 2 ranking.

2. Greenhouse gas emissions

A key part of a product's environmental footprint is the level of greenhouse emissions, expressed in kg of CO₂-equivalent per tonne of live weight production biomass. For aquaculture this is normally calculated for the entire production cycle up to the farm gate, and includes CO₂ and other energetic emissions from stock, as well as the energy used to raise stock, including harvesting, manufacturing and transporting inputs such as feed and chemotherapeutants.

The methodology involved is based on that developed by the STECF (STECF, 2023²⁹). The process for ranking the greenhouse emissions against established norms is shown in Figure 7. This shows that the 'feed level' is the key attribute involved. At Tier 1 levels, non-fed and extractive species would by default score highly³⁰ as no food consumption is involved and they may actually contribute to CO₂ sequestration. Depending upon the pre-assigned 'feed level' attribute category, they would then be scored, reflecting their feed level.

This would then go through a second scoring assessment that reflects the 'production system type' attribute, where the preliminary score would be adjusted up or down, depending upon the system type. For instance open-water systems would be scored down, as these are only accessible by boat and thus requiring inputs, staff and outputs to be transported to and from the site. Land-based flow-through systems would have their score increased, as they tend to be more energy efficient as no pumping is involved. RAS systems would have their score decreased, as they tend to have high environmental control-related energy costs. It should be emphasised that these scores are preliminary and for demonstration only but do provide an indication of the current thinking involved.

For Tier 2 the scoring would be refined using farm-level data. This could include robust Marine Fish Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) assessments using standardised methodologies e.g. PEF Category Rules (Anon, 2025). The UK's Seafish 'Seafood Carbon Emissions Profiling Tool'³¹ could also be used.

²⁹ Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (2023). Marketing standards: review of proposed sustainability criteria / indicators for aquaculture (STECF-22-13). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/93710, JRC132139.

³⁰ In Figure 2 they are scored 5, the highest in a scoring from 0 (lowest) to 5 (highest)

³¹ <https://seafoodcarbonprofilingtool.seafish.org/#!/>

Figure 7. Attribute application and scoring for 'Greenhouse gas emissions'

3. Effluent emissions to external waters

A second key part of a product's environmental footprint is the nature and impact of effluents from aquaculture production. The nature of these effluents can vary, but will include elevated suspended solids that can smother linked external environments, elevated nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus that can contribute to eutrophication as well as the chemical and chemotherapeutant substances (antibiotics, hormones, etc.) and their residues that can impact the functioning of linked ecosystems.

The methodology – which in some ways is similar to that for greenhouse gases as described above - is based on that developed by the STECF (STECF, 2023³²). The process for ranking the level of emissions against established norms is shown in Figure 8. This shows that the 'feed level' is the key attribute involved. At Tier 1 levels, non-fed and extractive species would by default score highly³³ as no food consumption is involved, organisms are often sessile or limited in mobility and metabolic waste is usually low. Depending upon the pre-assigned 'feed level' attribute category, they would then be scored reflecting their feed level.

This would then go through a second scoring assessment that reflects the 'production system type' attribute, where the preliminary score would be adjusted up or down, depending upon the system type. For instance, open-water systems (e.g. pens or extensive ponds) would be scored significantly down, as these limited or no control over water exchange with the external environment. Closed systems, such as tank or raceway culture could be marked up, as they afford a degree of control over water flow and can provide some level of filtration and water treatment, RAS systems will have their score increased substantially, as in theory at least, there is a high level of control over interchange with the internal (farm) environment and the external environment. It should be emphasised that these scores are preliminary and for demonstration only but again do provide an indication of the current thinking involved.

For Tier 2 the scoring would be refined using farm-level data. This could include robust Marine Fish Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) assessments using standardised methodologies e.g. PEF Category Rules (Anon, 2025). The candidate farming operations can also provide evidence that they exceed the Tier 1 norms, e.g. through additional water management and effluent treatment.

³² Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (2023). Marketing standards: review of proposed sustainability criteria / indicators for aquaculture (STECF-22-13). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/93710, JRC132139.

³³ In Figure 2 they are scored 5, the highest in a scoring from 0 (lowest) to 5 (highest)

Figure 8. Attribute application and scoring for effluent emissions

2.2 Nutrition and Health Indicators

D2.1 presented a comprehensive approach to nutrition and health indicators for aquafood. However, the application of these indicators—particularly in calculating nutritional quality scores for different aquafood products—requires high-quality, standardised food composition data. Aquafood composition databases, while improving in scope and detail, still present several largely undocumented challenges that must be considered when designing and implementing a fair scoring system. Challenges with nutrient composition data for aquafood include:

- **High species diversity and inconsistent classification**
Aquafoods represent an exceptionally diverse group, encompassing finfish, molluscs, cephalopods, crustaceans, seaweeds and other aquatic organisms. With more than 10,000 edible aquatic species globally, most food composition databases only cover a fraction of the species relevant to human diets. Moreover, inconsistent species identification and classification—across or even within databases—complicates comparison and undermines confidence in scoring outputs.
- **Sensitivity to biological and production variables**
Nutrient concentrations in aquatic foods are not fixed; they vary according to a wide range of biological and environmental factors, including species (most important determinant), edible part analysed (e.g., fillet, whole fish, muscle only, with or without skin), processing form (e.g., raw, frozen, dried, cooked), and production method (wild-caught versus farmed). Very few food composition datasets include sufficiently detailed metadata to allow meaningful distinction among these variables, and most lack consistency in how these are recorded. Without this information, nutrient values cannot be reliably compared across products or used with confidence in scoring algorithms.
- **Fragmentation and lack of harmonisation**
Numerous FCDBs now contain aquafood data (e.g., FoodEXplorer, AnFood/BioFoodComp, FishNutrients, uFish, SeaFoodData, AFCD), but their structures, nutrient sets, and data sources differ considerably in some respects and borrow/share data across others. There is often poor alignment in how food items are categorised, which nutrients are reported, and whether values are derived from empirical analyses or other means (e.g., literature or estimation), and if they are borrowed/shared. This fragmentation poses a major obstacle to the integration and use of these data in tools such as the VeriFish app.
- **Geographic and sampling bias**
Nutrient values might reflect samples collected from a limited number of geographic regions or under specific aquaculture conditions, while being applied more broadly. For instance, nutrient profiles for farmed tilapia derived from one country might not be applicable to products from other regions, particularly when feed, environment, and farming practices differ. There is now good evidence that, for example, omega 3: omega 6 values are different in farmed and wild salmon, favouring omega 6, which already occurs in European populations' diets in excess. This undermines the representativeness of data and the ability to generalise results within a scoring framework.

- Incomplete micronutrient coverage
While macronutrients (e.g., protein, total fat) are commonly reported, data on important omega-3 fatty acids (e.g., EPA and DHA) and micronutrients such as selenium, iodine, vitamin D, and vitamin B12 are far less available and often averaged or absent. These nutrients are central to the nutritional quality of many aquafood, and averaging/ omission limits the ability to construct a comprehensive and balanced nutritional quality score.

These challenges have direct implications for the calculation of combined nutritional quality values in VeriFish. Specifically, they underscore the need to ensure that data sources used for scoring are transparent, curated, and quality-controlled; use standardised approaches for edible portion selection (e.g., fillet, raw) to enable comparability; apply caps or weighting to avoid disproportionate influence from nutrients like EPA/DHA; and address data gaps explicitly, either through imputation methods, uncertainty flags, or exclusion criteria. Given the inconsistencies and limitations in currently available aquafood composition data, calculated nutrition quality values underpinning the scoring system must be designed to accommodate variability, avoid nutritional skew, and maintain fairness across species, particularly between fatty and lean fish. Efforts to harmonise databases, improve metadata, and expand the coverage of nutrient analyses—such as those led by the FAO, EuroFIR, and global communities of practice—are critical to improving the accuracy and credibility of future nutrition scoring in aquafood sustainability frameworks.

In this section, we are moving from the conceptual definition of indicators to the development of a practical approach to evaluate and facilitate communication of nutritional quality of aquafood. The aim is to provide a scientifically sound, transparent method that transforms complex nutrient data into values that can be combined with those from other pillars, offering an overall score for sustainability. To achieve this, the Framework is structured around:

- Indicators: nutrient-based criteria selected for relevance to human health and dietary quality. Examples include protein content, omega-3 fatty acid levels (EPA and DHA), sodium, saturated fat, and micronutrients such as selenium, iodine, and vitamin D. These indicators were chosen for their public health significance, measurability, and availability across different aquafood species (see D2.1 for details). Actual measured or reported amounts of individual nutrients per 100g edible portion are drawn from trusted sources, such as national food composition databases and standardised datasets (e.g., EuroFIR), ensuring consistency and reliability.
- Nutritional quality (per sea food product): it is not simply the raw nutrient content (e.g. 2.5g of EPA per 100g), but rather a derived, combined measure of how well a aquafood product performs across multiple nutrient indicators, and the calculated value needs to reflect the contribution of the product to a healthy diet, account for multiple nutrients simultaneously, and leave room for contaminants to be included in future, and avoid allowing a single nutrient (e.g., omega-3) dominate the score, allowing fair consideration across different aquafood types, particularly between fatty and lean fish.

Scores (D2.3 in due course) can be generated from a normalised evaluation of the nutrient value (nutritional quality), based on a target range or benchmark for each indicator. The score might be calculated using a distance to target approach, typically on a 0–5 Likert scale, and mapped onto a traffic light system for end-user communication. This allows nutrient values to be compared fairly across species and combined with environmental and socio-economic values.

This structure offers a nuanced but user-friendly way to compare aquafood based on their contribution to healthy diets. By translating raw nutrient data into interpretable scores, the VeriFish app and other outputs will support better consumer understanding and enable aquafood producers, retailers, and policymakers to promote products aligned with nutritional goals—without bias toward any single category of fish.

The identified indicators are grouped to the following tables according to their overall level of relevance, with all indicators within each table considered as equally important.

Table 5. highly relevant nutrition and health indicators

Highly relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Carbohydrate	Macronutrient that provides energy
Cholesterol	Waxy, fat-like substance present in cell membranes and involved in hormones and vitamin D production
Chloride	Electrolyte that helps maintain fluid balance, blood pressure, and proper muscle and nerve function
Energy	Caloric content provided by macronutrients (carbohydrates, fats, proteins)
Monounsaturated fatty acids	Monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs); healthy fats with one double bond; associated with reduced risk of CVD
Saturated fatty acids	Saturated fatty acids; fats with no double bonds between carbon atoms; typically solid at room temperature, found in animal products and some plant oils.
Fat	Macronutrient that provides energy, supports cell growth; essential for absorption and storage of fat-soluble vitamins
Iodine (I)	Mineral necessary for thyroid hormone production

Highly relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Sodium (Na)	Electrolyte that regulates fluid balance, blood pressure, and nerve and muscle function
Protein	Macronutrient made of amino acids, essential for building and repairing tissues, enzymes, hormones, and immune function
Selenium (se)	Mineral with bioactive properties, important for thyroid function and immune system support
EPA 20:5(n-3)	Eicosapentaenoic acid; long-chain omega-3 fatty acid found in fish; associated with reduced risk of CVD and inflammation
DHA 22:6(n-3)	Docosahexaenoic acid; long-chain omega-3 fatty acid found in fish; essential for brain development and function, and eye health

Table 6. medium relevant nutrition and health indicators

Medium relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Biotin	B-vitamin (B7) essential for metabolism, fatty acid synthesis, and maintaining healthy skin and hair
Calcium (Ca)	Mineral crucial for bone health, muscle function, nerve signalling, and blood clotting
Copper (Cu)	Mineral important for iron metabolism, immune function, and formation of red blood cells and connective tissue
Iron (Fe)	mineral essential for forming haemoglobin in red blood cells, transporting oxygen, and supporting metabolism and immunity

Medium relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Folate	Folate and/or folic acid; B-vitamin (B9) essential for DNA synthesis, cell division, and fetal development
Potassium (K)	Electrolyte that helps maintain fluid balance, supports muscle contractions, and regulates nerve signals and blood pressure
Magnesium (Mg)	Mineral involved in over enzymatic reactions, including energy production, protein synthesis, and muscle and nerve function
Manganese (Mn)	Mineral that has a role in bone formation, blood clotting, etc.
Niacin	B-vitamin (B3) essential for energy metabolism, DNA repair, and maintaining healthy skin and nerves
Phosphorus (P)	Mineral vital for bone and teeth formation, energy production, and cell membrane function
Pantathenic acid	B-vitamin (B5) crucial for synthesizing and metabolising proteins, carbohydrates, and fats
Retinol	Form of vitamin A important for vision, immune function, and skin health
Riboflavin	B-vitamin (B2) essential for energy production, red blood cell formation, and the metabolism of fats, some medicines and steroids
Thiamin	B-vitamin (B1) essential for energy metabolism and the proper functioning of the nervous system
Vitamin A	Fat-soluble vitamin important for vision, immune function, and cell growth
Vitamin B12	B-vitamin necessary for red blood cell formation, DNA synthesis, and nervous system function
Vitamin B6	B-vitamin involved in protein metabolism, red blood cell production, and neurotransmitter synthesis

Medium relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Vitamin C	Ascorbic acid; bioactive water-soluble vitamin , essential for collagen synthesis, immune function, and wound healing
Vitamin D	Fat-soluble vitamin important for calcium absorption, bone health, and immune function
Vitamin E	Fat-soluble vitamin with bioactive properties, protecting cells from damage and supporting immune function
Zinc (Zn)	Mineral crucial for immune function, wound healing, DNA synthesis, and cell division

Table 7. low relevant nutrition and health indicators

Low relevant indicators	
Indicator	Description
Ash	Inorganic mineral residue left after the complete combustion of organic matter in food
Polyunsaturated fatty acids	Polyunsaturated fatty acids(PUFAs); healthy fats with multiple double bonds; associated with reduced risk of CVD

2.3 Social and Economic Indicators

There is an important distinction between the environmental and nutritional pillars of sustainability and the social and economic indicators. This difference lies primarily in the level of detail and reliability of data available for public-level assessments.

For environmental indicators, such as a science-based stock assessment for North Sea cod, robust, publicly available data allows for well-informed assumptions about the sustainability of the fishery as a whole. For

example, if a stock assessment confirms healthy cod populations, this can generally be applied to cod caught by all vessels operating in that fishery. However, the same level of detailed, fishery-wide assessment is not possible for most social and economic indicators. Conditions can vary significantly between vessels or farms within the same fishery or region. For this reason, in particular social assessments often rely on risk-level evaluations based on fishery-, country-, or region-level data. Only detailed, site-specific assessments, at the vessel, farm, or company level, can provide reliable, measurable insights, and such data is rarely publicly available.

For example, if a producer country has not ratified key **ILO conventions** (e.g. the United States), the risk score may be high - even if the country has strong domestic labour protections that are not captured in the data source. Conversely, a vessel owner may implement excellent labour practices, but if their flag State is rated high risk, and there is no verified traceability, the product could still score poorly. In such cases, the system cannot reward good practices without supply chain transparency and validated evidence

The following table summarizes the indicators for the social and economic pillar, grouped into the following categories: governance, labour practices and rights, health and safety of workers and discrimination and indigenous peoples.

Table 8. Social and Economic Indicators

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Sector	Attribute
01	Not on an IUU fishing list	Governance	Capture Fisheries	Vessel
02	Not considered to be a Flag of Convenience	Governance	Capture Fisheries	Country
03	Corruption	Governance	Cross-sector	Country
04	Subsidies: harmful vs. supportive	Governance	Capture Fisheries	Country
05	Port State controls	Governance	Capture Fisheries	Country
06	Wages and working conditions	Labour Practices & Rights	Cross-sector	Country
07	Workers' rights and union representation	Labour Practices & Rights	Cross-sector	Country
08	Prevention of child labour	Labour Practices & Rights	Cross-sector	Country
09	Prevention of forced labour, modern slavery & human trafficking	Labour Practices & Rights	Cross-sector	Country

	Indicator	Sub-pillar	Sector	Attribute
10	Access to healthcare and medical facilities	Health and Safety of Workers	Capture Fisheries	Country
11	Occupational Health & Safety at work	Health and Safety of Workers	Cross-sector	Country
12	Work place training	Health and Safety of Workers	Cross-sector	Country
13	Equality & prevention of discrimination	Discrimination and Indigenous peoples	Cross-sector	Country
14	Respect for indigenous peoples	Discrimination and Indigenous peoples	Cross-sector	Country

Indicator 01: Not on an IUU fishing list

Vessels should not be on an IUU vessel list. Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is caught by a vessel that appears on an official IUU fishing vessel list published by a Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO) or other recognized authority. Listing is taken as verified evidence of serious breaches of fisheries rules, often linked to broader risks such as labour rights abuses. If vessel-level traceability is not available, the system may need to default to country- or fishery-level risk assessment instead.

When vessels are caught IUU fishing they are put on a list. IUU fishing is linked to human & labour rights abuses. Assessment will use official IUU vessel lists as primary data sources.

Why is the indicator framed in this way? Being listed as an IUU vessel typically indicates serious non-compliance with fishing rules, often involving illegal operations, unsafe practices, or exploitation of crew. IUU lists are formal, publicly maintained and involve a recognized, evidence-based process so they are a strong legal and compliance risk signal. Unlike country-level proxies, this indicator allows direct assessment at the vessel level, wherever possible.

Indicator 02: Not considered to be a Flag of Convenience

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is caught by vessels flagged to a country recognized as operating a flag of convenience (FoC) registry. Flags of convenience are often associated with weaker oversight of labour standards, vessel safety, and environmental regulations.

If flag states are assessed to have weak control & enforcement over vessels fishing under their flags then they are featured on various lists Published by different organisations. Assessments will reference FoC registers, such as those maintained by the International Transport Workers' Federation (ITF), to determine risk.

Why is the indicator framed this way? FoC countries are typically those where owners register vessels to avoid stricter regulations in their home countries; associated with higher risks of IUU fishing, forced labour, and poor working conditions. The ITF FoC list is internationally recognized and widely cited in due diligence systems (for shipping, fisheries, and beyond). Without strong oversight from the flag State, accountability gaps increase throughout the supply chain.

Indicator 03: Corruption

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in or landed into a country with high levels of perceived corruption, as identified in the Transparency International Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI). High corruption levels can undermine enforcement of fisheries regulations, labour rights, and environmental protections.

High levels of corruption may indicate weak enforcement of labour laws and increased risks of rights violations in supply chains. Country-level CPI scores will be used as a proxy for assessing governance risks affecting aquafood supply chains.

Why is the indicator framed in this way? Corruption directly impacts the effectiveness of fisheries management, port inspections, labour law enforcement, and traceability. The CPI is internationally recognized and annually updated, providing a comparable corruption risk score for nearly every country globally. Even where good laws exist, weak governance due to corruption can result in IUU fishing, forced labour, and unregulated landings.

Indicator 04: Subsidies: harmful vs. supportive

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is caught by vessels flagged to, or landed into, a country that has been identified as providing harmful fisheries subsidies, particularly those linked to capacity-enhancing activities such as fuel subsidies, vessel construction support, or operating subsidies.

Aquafood should be considered at lower risk if it is caught by vessels flagged to, or landed into, a country that has been identified as providing primarily supportive fisheries subsidies, particularly those aimed at sustainability, resource management, environmental protection, safety training, scientific research, or community development.

- Harmful: Refers to public subsidies that contribute to overcapacity or overfishing, potentially undermining stock sustainability and increasing risk of labour abuses.
- Supportive: Captures government financial support for sustainable practices such as safety training, income diversification, vessel modernisation, or research.
- High Risk: Country is identified as providing high levels of harmful subsidies (according to OECD or WTO classification).

- Medium Risk: Country provides mixed subsidies, including some harmful and some supportive (e.g., investment in sustainability and research).
- Low Risk: Country primarily provides beneficial subsidies (e.g., fisheries management, safety, stock research) and minimal or no harmful ones.

Why is this indicator framed this way? Because in WTO and OECD reporting, not all subsidies are classified equally; capacity-enhancing ones are the issue. Some support fisheries management, scientific research, training, etc., and are seen as positive.

Indicator 05: Port State controls

Aquafood should be considered higher risk if it is landed into a country that has not ratified the PSMA. It measures whether a country is a party to the Port State Measures Agreement and actively implements inspections of foreign fishing vessels in its ports. Ratification is used as a minimum indicator of a country's commitment to preventing IUU fishing through effective port controls, acknowledging that implementation effectiveness may vary and is not consistently documented.

Indicator 06: Wages and working conditions

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country assessed as having widespread violations of workers' rights, including inadequate protection for fair wages and decent working conditions.

It assesses whether minimum wages, decent working conditions, and legal protections are upheld in the workplace. Assessments will draw on the ITUC Global Rights Index and national labour law frameworks, recognising that country-level conditions are used as a proxy for workplace standards in the absence of vessel- or farm-specific data.

Why is the indicator framed this way? The ITUC Global Rights Index ranks countries annually from 1 (best) to 5+ (worst) based on respect for workers' rights, including wages, unionisation, collective bargaining, and safe conditions. National labour law databases (like those maintained by the ILO) can provide supporting evidence if needed.

Indicator 07: Workers' rights and union representation

Aquafood should be considered at higher social risk if it is produced in a country that has not ratified key ILO conventions on freedom of association and collective bargaining, or where the ITUC Global Rights Index indicates serious restrictions on workers' rights to organise, join unions, and negotiate collectively. It evaluates the extent to which workers are able to organise, bargain collectively and join trade unions freely.

Why is the indicator framed this way? ILO Convention 87 (Freedom of Association) and Convention 98 (Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining) are core labour rights conventions. The ITUC Global Rights Index measures how well those rights are actually protected/enforced in practice, not just whether a country has

signed the paper. Together, they give a proxy for the likelihood that fishers, farmworkers, and aquafood workers can defend their rights. Country-level data is used as a proxy in the absence of verified vessel- or company-specific information.

Indicator 08: Prevention of child labour

Aquafood should be considered at higher social risk if it is produced in a country where child labour is known or suspected to occur in the fishing or aquaculture sectors, or where the country has not ratified key international conventions aimed at preventing child labour (138 and 182). It indicates whether countries prohibit and take active steps to prevent child labour in fisheries and aquaculture. Assessments will use the U.S. Department of Labor's Child Labor Reports, ILO ratification records, and enforcement data as references, recognising that country-level conditions are used as a proxy where direct supply chain evidence is unavailable.

Why is the indicator framed this way? ILO Convention No. 138 – Minimum Age Convention (1973) and No. 182 – Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention (1999) are core conventions. The US DOL Child Labor List specifically flags sectors where child labour has been reported or is suspected, including fishing and aquafood in some countries. ILO's child labour databases give additional verification, especially about national laws and enforcement. Even if child labour exists in one part of a country and not another, without full traceability, you must assume that sector-level risk applies.

Indicator 09: Prevention of forced labour, modern slavery & human trafficking

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country identified as having significant risks of forced labour, modern slavery, or human trafficking in the fishing or aquaculture sectors, or where national protections are weak. It measures efforts to combat forced labour and trafficking, including ratified conventions and implementation. Assessments will use the U.S. Trafficking in Persons (TIP) Report rankings, Global Slavery Index risk scores, and ILO data, recognising that country-level assessments are applied in the absence of vessel-, farm-, or company-specific information.

Why is the indicator framed in this way? The TIP Report ranks countries into Tiers 1, 2, 2 Watch List, 3 based on how well governments are addressing trafficking (including forced labour at sea). The Global Slavery Index provides broader national risk scores for the prevalence of forced labour and human trafficking. The ILO provides information on national legislation, ratification of relevant conventions (especially Forced Labour Conventions C29 and C105), and enforcement actions.

Indicator 10: Access to healthcare and medical facilities

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country where there is limited legal protection or enforcement to ensure fishers and aquaculture workers have access to healthcare services, both at sea and on land. It indicates the availability of health services and medical care for fishers at sea and on shore. Assessments will reference ratification of the ILO Work in Fishing Convention (C188) and

relevant national regulations, recognising that country-level legal frameworks are used as a proxy in the absence of supply chain-specific evidence.

Why is the indicator framed this way? ILO C188 requires countries to ensure medical care for fishers both offshore (on board) and ashore, including standards for medical equipment, first aid training, and emergency response. Many national health systems also regulate whether workers can access hospitals, clinics, or occupational health services, particularly important for fishers operating in remote areas.

Indicator 11: Occupational H&S at work

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country where occupational health and safety (OHS) standards are weak, poorly enforced, or not aligned with international norms. It assesses legal and institutional protections for occupational safety and accident prevention. Assessments will draw on ratification of key ILO conventions, notably the Occupational Safety and Health Convention (C155), and review available national OHS regulations, recognizing that country-level frameworks are used as a proxy for workplace safety conditions in the absence of verified supply chain-specific data.

Why is the indicator framed in this way? ILO Convention 155 is the central international treaty requiring countries to establish and enforce comprehensive national OHS frameworks. National OHS regulations (labour codes, fisheries/aquaculture-specific safety laws) are highly variable, but ratification of C155 indicates a legal commitment to worker safety. Many accidents at sea and in aquaculture relate directly to poor national safety standards (equipment, training, accident reporting, etc.).

Indicator 12: Work place training

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country where there is limited legal obligation or enforcement around workplace training, including occupational safety, skills development, and emergency preparedness for fisheries and aquaculture workers. It looks at the existence of legal requirements or initiatives for worker training and upskilling. Assessments will draw on national labour legislation and ILO references to training standards, using country-level frameworks as a proxy where direct supply chain training data is unavailable. Why is the indicator framed this way? Training is a crucial part of health, safety, and decent work especially for high-risk industries like fishing and aquaculture. The ILO emphasises the importance of workplace training in the Occupational Safety and Health Convention (C155) and sectoral guidance like the Work in Fishing Convention (C188). National labour laws often require or omit mandatory training for safety, first aid, equipment use, etc.

Indicator 13: Equality & prevention of discrimination

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country where legal protections against discrimination based on gender, ethnicity, or other social factors are weak or poorly enforced. It assesses laws and enforcement mechanisms against discrimination based on gender, ethnicity, etc. Assessments will draw on ratification of key ILO conventions (C100 and C111), national equality laws, and international

indicators such as the OECD Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI), recognizing that country-level conditions are used as a proxy for workplace equality in the absence of direct supply chain data. Why is the indicator framed this way? ILO Convention 100 focuses on equal pay for equal work between men and women, and C111 addresses non-discrimination in employment and occupation based on race, gender, religion, political opinion, national extraction, or social origin. OECD SIGI measures discrimination in laws, social norms, and practices across countries; helpful for broader understanding beyond just legal ratification. Discrimination is often systemic and not easily observed at the vessel or farm level, so national laws and performance serve as the best available proxy.

Indicator 14: Respect for indigenous peoples

Aquafood should be considered at higher risk if it is produced in a country where the rights of indigenous peoples are not adequately recognised or protected, particularly regarding traditional fishing rights, participation in decision-making, and protection of cultural heritage. It evaluates national frameworks that recognize and protect the rights of indigenous communities. Assessments will be based on ratification of the ILO Convention 169, analysis of national legal protections, and relevant UN Special Rapporteur reports, recognizing that country-level frameworks are used as a proxy in the absence of direct supply chain data. Why is the indicator framed in this way? ILO Convention 169 is the main international treaty specifically protecting the rights of indigenous and tribal peoples. UN Special Rapporteur reports highlight actual practices and systemic violations where laws may be absent or poorly enforced. Respect for indigenous peoples often includes access to traditional fishing grounds, participation in fisheries management, and protection against displacement; all highly relevant for ethical aquafood sourcing.

3 Environmental Indicators data sources

The main focus of environmental indicators is to minimise ecological harm and to promote sustainable use of resources within capture fisheries and aquaculture. They will draw on scientifically validated and widely used data sources, such as biodiversity and ecological databases, fishery catch records, fisheries and maritime regulations, etc. The following table summarizes the inventoried key data sources, which are described in detail in the next subsections.

Table 9. Inventory of environmental indicators data sources

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level	Capture Fisheries	Aquaculture
Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)	stocks, fisheries, biomass, fishing pressure, fishing gears, fishing area	Protected	✓	
FishBase	species (fish), ecology, biology	Public	✓	✓
SeaLifeBase	species (non-fish), ecology, biology	Public	✓	✓
Sea Around Us	impact of fisheries on marine ecosystems	Public	✓	
IUCN Red List of Threatened Species	species (threatened), ecology	Public	✓	✓
Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)	species (threatened)	Public	✓	✓
Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS)	species (threatened)	Public	✓	✓
Data Collection Framework (DCF)	stock assessment	Public	✓	
EMODNET Biology	species occurrence data, species traits, biomass, abundance, habitat	Public	✓	✓
WISE-Marine	non-indigenous species, eutrophication, environment	Public	✓	✓

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level	Capture Fisheries	Aquaculture
European Nature Information System (EUNIS)	species, habitats, protected areas in Europe	Public	✓	
Fair-Fish Database	fish welfare	Public	✓	✓
ByCatch Management Information System	ByCatch in tuna fisheries	Public	✓	
IUU (Illegal, Unreported, Unregulated) vessel lists	illegal, unreported & unregulated fishing activity	Public	✓	

3.1 Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)

The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)³⁴ is an international initiative aimed at improving transparency and traceability in global fisheries and aquaculture. It serves as a comprehensive, centralized database that provides standardized and scientifically validated information on fish stocks and fisheries worldwide. The GRSF is designed to support sustainable fisheries management by offering reliable data to stakeholders, including governments, industry players, researchers, and conservation organizations.

GRSF integrates data from four different data sources, owned by different stakeholders, in a knowledge base (the GRSF KB). These data sources are: (a) Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS)³⁵, (b) RAM Legacy Stock Assessment database³⁶, (c) FishSource³⁷, and (d) records from FAO SDG 14.4.1 Questionnaire³⁸. They contain complementary information (both conceptually and geographically) and all of them contribute to the overall aim of building a comprehensive and transparent global reference set of stocks and fisheries records that will boost regional and global stocks and fisheries status and trend monitoring as well as responsible consumer practices.

³⁴ Tzitzikas, Y., Marketakis, Y., Minadakis, N., Mountantonakis, M., Candela, L., Mangiacrapa, F., Pagano, P., Perciante, C., Castelli, D., Taconet, M. and Gentile, A., 2017, September. Towards a Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries. In HAICTA (pp. 328-340).

³⁵ <https://firms.fao.org/firms/en/home>

³⁶ <https://www.ramlegacy.org>

³⁷ <https://www.fishsource.org/>

³⁸ <https://www.fao.org/sustainable-development-goals-data-portal/data/indicators/1441-fish-stocks-sustainability/>

The main challenge for the construction of the GRSF is the ability to semantically integrate data coming from different data sources. To tackle this challenge, it relies on semantic web technologies and use domain-specific top-level ontologies, which provide (a) consistent abstractions or specifications of concepts included in all data models or ontologies of marine data sources and (b) the necessary properties to make GRSF a coherent source of facts relating observational data with the respective spatiotemporal context and categorical domain knowledge. Furthermore, to ensure that GRSF contents are up-to-date, it invokes a refresh workflow³⁹ that collects the most recent updates from its corresponding remote data sources and reconstructs the knowledge base.

Information in GRSF revolves around stocks and fisheries records. A stock is a population of a given species (or group of species) in a given area that is regarded as a unit for the purposes of assessment and management. A fishery is described as the activity leading to the harvesting of fish. GRSF stocks are identified with respect to: (a) the species they involve, and (b) the assessment area they refer to. GRSF fisheries are identified with respect to: (a) the species they involve, (b) the fishing area they refer to, (c) the corresponding flag state of the fishing activity, (d) the management authority in charge of the fishing activity and (e) the fishing method. GRSF creates consolidated records (that are the results of integrating resources from different data sources) with time-series describing their time-dependent information in terms of reported catches and landings, fishing pressure, abundance level, etc. GRSF resources are exposed in different forms: (a) through a catalogue of a Virtual Research Environment (VRE), operated on top of D4Science infrastructure⁴⁰, (b) through a dedicated RESTFull API⁴¹ (c) through the SPARQL endpoint of the GRSF KB⁴². In general, GRSF KB contents are publicly available, however, the time-series of GRSF records are generally protected.

More specifically, through the GRSF API, one can collect information about the stocks, the fisheries and their associated information (i.e. catches, landings, abundance level of stocks, etc.). A few indicative API calls demonstrating how GRSF contents are exposed are the following:

- Get stock data about Brill (species with scientific name *Scophthalmus rhombus*), captured in the North Sea.
https://isl.ics.forth.gr/grsf/grsf-api/resources/getstocks?species_code=BLL&area_code=27.4&area_type=fao . It is worth noting that this GRSF record is derived from all the four different data sources that are contributing to GRSF, and contains timeseries about abundance level, fishing pressure, catches and landed volume.

³⁹ Marketakis, Y., Tzitzikas, Y., Gentile, A., Van Niekerk, B., and Taconet, M., 2020. *On the Evolution of Semantic Warehouses: The Case of Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries*. 14th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research, Special Track on Metadata & Semantics for Agriculture, Food & Environment (AgroSEM'20) Madrid, 2020

⁴⁰ <https://services.d4science.org/group/grsf>

⁴¹ <https://isl.ics.forth.gr/grsf/grsf-api>

⁴² <https://isl.ics.forth.gr/grsf/sparql>

- Get fisheries data about Beaked redfish (species with scientific name *Sebastes mentella*), in Norwegian Sea, https://isl.ics.forth.gr/grsf/grsf-api/resources/getfisheries?species_code=REB&area_code=27.2.a.2&area_type=fao

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The key entities that can be used for the purposes of the framework are particular attributes of records, describing the exploitation rate of different stocks, fishing effort dimensions, and the overall state and trend of stocks and fisheries. The following figure demonstrates part of the information about a stock record describing Hake in the Adriatic Sea. GRSF is a credible source providing information on overfished species, depleted stocks and sustainable fisheries. GRSF is a key and valuable source for the development of the framework, since it consolidates and harmonizes data from several authoritative sources related to fish stocks and fisheries. By integrating them into a unified structure, GRSF enhances the data accessibility, consistency and traceability. We should also mention that the VeriFish Knowledge Base will be built on top of GRSF KB; more details about this are given in deliverables *D2.4* and *D2.5*.

Merluccius merluccius - Northern Adriatic - Southern Adriatic PRIVATE

Short Name: Hake Adriatic Sea
 GRSF Semantic Identifier: asfis:HKE+gfc:17,gfc:18
 Record URL: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GRSF_Admin/e0902f54-b5d9-312a-accd-85034e1ce5ff

[Citation](#)

Map Preview

Tags

Assessment Unit

Code 17 System gfc:17 Name Northern Adriatic

Code 18 System gfc:18 Name Southern Adriatic

Code 37 System fao Name Mediterranean and Black Sea

Code HKE Classification System ASFIS Scientific Name Merluccius merluccius

Unspecified

not connected

without similar records

Stock Identity

Field	Value
Assessment Area	Code: 17, System: gfc:17, Name: Northern Adriatic
Assessment Area	Code: 18, System: gfc:18, Name: Southern Adriatic
Database Source	FAO SDG 14.4.1 Questionnaire
Database Source	Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS)
Database Source	RAM Legacy Stock Assessment Database
GRSF Semantic Identifier	asfis:HKE+gfc:17,gfc:18
GRSF Stock Name	Merluccius merluccius - Northern Adriatic - Southern Adriatic
GRSF Type	Assessment Unit
Intersecting FAO Major Fishing Areas	Code: 37, System: fao, Name: Mediterranean and Black Sea
Jurisdictional Distribution	Unspecified
Short Name	Hake Adriatic Sea
Species	Code: HKE, Classification System: ASFIS, Scientific Name: Merluccius merluccius

Figure 9. Sample of information about a stock record describing Hake in the Adriatic Sea retrieved from the GRSF

3.2 FishBase

FishBase⁴³ is the globally most accessed specialised database about marine and freshwater fishes, providing information about life cycle and history, population dynamics, ecology, distribution, taxonomy, human uses and several other aspects of fish biology. It is widely used and exploited by other scientific databases, research institutions, and conservation organizations. It integrates data from a variety of sources, including scientific literature, fisheries surveys, and expert contributions, making it a robust and reliable repository of ichthyological knowledge. FishBase is continuously updated with new information contributed by experts in the field, making it an invaluable resource for the fisheries domain. Currently (February 2025) it includes descriptions for 35,800 species, 330,300 common names in different languages used in various countries, 65,100 pictures and references to 63,000 scientific works.

Figure 10. FishBase public portal

FishBase is publicly available without any restrictions or embargoes on the data. This open-access policy is in line with the database’s mission to promote the dissemination of scientific knowledge and support global efforts in fisheries management and biodiversity conservation. The main access method is through the website; FishBase delivers its contents through a series of mirroring websites that provide a user-friendly

⁴³ <https://fishbase.org/>

interface for searching and browsing data. Moreover, there is an API⁴⁴ that supports searching a specific part of FishBase (i.e. regarding species names and classification). In addition, data can be exposed directly from FishBase website in XML format (e.g. <https://www.fishbase.se/webservice/comnames/ComNamesXML.php?Genus=Mullus&Species=barbatus> for delivering common names of red mullet, and <https://www.fishbase.se/webservice/Occurrence/PointData.php?Genus=Mullus&Species=barbatus> for georeferenced occurrence records of that species).

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FishBase is a very important source for VeriFish, because it provides the foundational data needed for effective fisheries management and conservation. The detailed information on fish populations, their habitats and historical data, helps fisheries managers make informed decisions that promote sustainable fishing practices. Moreover, its rich vocabulary of common names of species in different languages and countries is a strong asset towards identifying and communicating fish-related information for different audiences.

3.3 SeaLifeBase

SeaLifeBase⁴⁵ is a complementary database to FishBase, since it provides information about various marine life organisms that are not included in FishBase. More specifically, FishBase includes only finfish⁴⁶, while SeaLifeBase all the others. Similarly to its complementary source, it offers detailed species profiles, ecological information, and distribution data. Currently (April 2025) it includes descriptions for 71,700 species, 60,000 common names in different languages used in various countries, 15,700 pictures and references to 40,300 scientific works

Similar to FishBase, SeaLifeBase is publicly available through its official website offering a user-friendly interface for searching and browsing data. SeaLifeBase is particularly useful for promoting sustainability in fisheries and aquaculture by providing accurate information on species' distribution and ecological roles, since it helps in setting quotas, protecting habitats, and managing stocks sustainably. Moreover, it enables policymakers to use the database to develop strategies for sustainable seafood production while ensuring the long-term health of marine ecosystems. In addition, it contains links to external sources for more detailed-fisheries related activities such as FAO FIRMS (for stock assessments), FishSource (for fisheries-related data), Sea Around Us (for marine ecosystems, etc.)

Why is it important for VeriFish?

⁴⁴ <https://www.fishbase.co/api/readme.txt>

⁴⁵ <https://www.sealifebase.org/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.iss-foundation.org/glossary/finfish/>

Despite its focus on non-fish species, SeaLifeBase is a useful data source for the purposes of VeriFish, since it provides data on the broader marine ecosystem, which supports fish populations and fisheries. This knowledge is important for developing holistic conservation strategies that consider the entire ecosystem, not just the target fish species.

3.4 Sea Around Us

The Sea Around Us⁴⁷ is a research initiative and data repository on global fisheries and marine ecosystems. It provides comprehensive data on fish catches, fishing effort, and the impact of fisheries on marine biodiversity. The project put emphasis on historical data, providing catch time series starting in 1950, and related series (e.g., landed value and catch by flag state, fishing sector and catch type), and fisheries-related information on every maritime country (e.g., government subsidies, marine biodiversity).

⁴⁷ <https://www.seaaroundus.org/>

Catches by Taxon in the waters of Cape Verde

[Download Data](#)

[Feedback](#)

Figure 11. Example of interactive graph from the Sea Around Us portal

Data from Sea Around Us is publicly and freely available granted that the source is properly acknowledged. Its data can be accessed through the official website, which provides facilities for searching and browsing data, as well as various tools and visualizations such as interactive maps and graphs to provide a better exploration of the data. The following figure demonstrates catch time series for different species measured in tonnes, for the period 1950-2019, that can also be downloaded for further analysis.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

Sea Around Us, provides information that is necessary for assessing the health of global fisheries and the impacts of fishing on marine ecosystems. More specifically, by reconstructing historical catch data and analysing current trends, it helps to identify overfished species, depleted stocks and areas where fishing practices need to be improved.

3.5 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species & Relevant sources

The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species⁴⁸ is an inventory of the global conservation status of plant, animal, and fungi species. Maintained by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), it is one of the most authoritative sources of information on species' extinction risk. It categorizes species into various threat levels, ranging from "Least Concern" to "Extinct," based on rigorous scientific assessments, and includes detailed information on species' population trends, distribution, habitats, threats, and conservation actions. The IUCN Red List is widely used by governments, NGOs, researchers, and conservationists to guide biodiversity conservation efforts, policy-making, and resource allocation.

The main entities within the IUCN Red List that are commonly used include (a) species profiles, with details on individual species, taxonomy, ecology and threats, (b) threat categories that help identify species at risk of extinction and prioritize conservation actions, (c) population trends and distribution maps, offering insights into species' historical and current ranges, and (d) conservation actions including recommended measures to mitigate threats and support species recovery.

The IUCN Red List is a publicly available resource, promoting open access to its data to support global conservation efforts, ensuring that the information can be used by different disciplines. Although data are publicly available and can be freely used, IUCN encourages proper citation and acknowledgement of the Red List as a source. Its resources are available through its user-friendly website, where users can explore species profiles and threat categories as well as search using various criteria. In addition, IUCN supports directly downloading entire datasets, as well as accessing them through an API⁴⁹. The following figure demonstrates the geographic range of a critically endangered species (e.g. Angelshark) and the geographic range of its occurrences. These data resources can be downloaded either from the website of the IUCN Red List, or through the API.

⁴⁸ <https://www.iucnredlist.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://api.iucnredlist.org/>

Figure 12. Geographic range of a critically endangered species from the IUCN Red List

Additional data sources for ETP species include the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)⁵⁰ and the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS)⁵¹.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The IUCN Red List provides critical information on the conservation status of marine species, including many fish and invertebrates that are targeted by fisheries. By identifying species at risk of extinction or population decline, it helps fisheries management stakeholders to implement measures to prevent overexploitation and promote sustainable fishing practices.

⁵⁰ <https://cites.org/ena>

⁵¹ <https://www.cms.int/>

3.6 EMODNET Biology datasets

EMODnet biology is a thematic group of EMODnet providing free access to data on temporal and spatial distribution of marine species and species traits from all European regional seas. It is built upon the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS)⁵² and the European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS)⁵³. It brings together biogeographic data collected within European marine waters, or by European researchers and institutes outside Europe. It focuses on taxonomy and distribution records in space and time and offers a number of online tools to easily query and visualise the data. By the time of writing these lines, EurOBIS holds more than 1,200 datasets, representing 71.589 species and more than 45 million occurrence records.

The contents of EMODnet biology revolve around the following categories: (a) species occurrence data (e.g. distribution records for commercially important fish species), (b) species abundance and biomass data (c) species traits (e.g. biological and ecological traits of marine species), (d) habitat and biotope data, (e) long-term biological time-series. EMODnet Biology resources can be browsed through the EMODnet Map Viewer⁵⁴ as well as through the EMODnet Products Catalogue⁵⁵.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

It provides accurate data (i.e. abundance and biomass) that help track fish populations over time. Moreover, it facilitates assessing the ecosystem health by assessing information on species distribution, trophic interactions and invasive species monitoring. Finally, through the long-term biological time series it supports the detection of shifts in fish distributions due to various reasons (e.g. temperature changes).

3.7 Data Collection Framework (DCF)

The EU Data Collection Framework (DCF)⁵⁶ is a legal and operational system designed to collect, manage, and provide scientific data for fisheries management and marine ecosystem assessments. It supports the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)⁵⁷ by ensuring high-quality and harmonized data collection across EU member states. It covers a wide range of data, including information on fish stocks, fishing activities, fleet characteristics, and various social and economic aspects of fisheries. The main entities within DCF that are commonly used include fish stock assessments (e.g. status of commercial fish populations, biomass, fishing mortality, etc.), catch and effort data, fishing gears and fleet data (e.g. vessel characteristics, capacity).

Aggregated data resources and scientific assessments are derived from DCF collected data, in the form of reports, databases and online data resources. The EU and its related agencies, such as the European

⁵² <https://www.marinespecies.org/>

⁵³ <https://www.eurobis.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/>

⁵⁵

https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geo/network/srv/eng/catalogo.search#/search?facet.q=sourceCatalog%2Fd186c17b-a362-4348-aa58-163be5295306&resultType=details&sortBy=sortDate&from=1&to=20&fast=index&_content_type=json

⁵⁶ <https://dcf.ec.europa.eu/>

⁵⁷ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/policy/common-fisheries-policy-cfp_en

Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA) and the Scientific, Technical, and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF)⁵⁸, play key roles in disseminating this information. Some datasets are available for download in formats like CSV, Excel, or PDF reports, while others might require the use of sophisticated software and tools.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The Data Collection Framework enables the aggregation of data resources in a standardized and systematic manner, ensuring its quality and validation, which enables accurate assessments of fish stocks and their impacts on fishing activities.

3.8 WISE-Marine

The EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)⁵⁹ is a European directive established in 2008, aimed to protect and sustainably manage Europe's marine environments and achieve or maintain a good environmental status by 2020. Although there were no specific targets and measures, the EU member states were encouraged to develop their own marine strategies with the overall objective of protecting or restoring marine environments, as well as reducing and preventing inputs to the marine environment to phase out pollution. The directive covers different aspects including biodiversity, non-indigenous species, commercial fish and shellfish, food webs, eutrophication, seafloor integrity, hydrographic conditions, environmental contaminants, contaminants in aquafood, marine litter, and introduction of energy including underwater noise.

MSFD data resources and reports are publicly available, as transparency is the key principle of the EU directive. Different member states submitted their reports and updates which are then aggregated, compiled and published by corresponding organizations such as the European Environment Agency (EEA). A dedicated platform aiming to support MSFD, is WISE-Marine (Water Information System for Europe - Marine)⁶⁰. WISE-Marine is a European web-based platform designed to provide access to data, indicators, and information related to the marine environment, focusing on Europe's seas as well as on the actions that can be taken to protect and conserve them.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

MSFD data resources are highly relevant since they directly address the health of European marine ecosystems by monitoring and managing factors such as biodiversity, pollution, fish stocks and others.

⁵⁸ https://stecf.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁵⁹ DIRECTIVE 2008/56/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL

⁶⁰ <https://water.europa.eu/marine>

3.9 European Nature Information System (EUNIS)

The European Nature Information Systems (EUNIS)⁶¹ is a pan-European database and reference system developed by the European Environment Agency (EEA), that provides information on Europe's natural habitats, species, and protected areas. It supports environmental policies, conservation efforts, and biodiversity monitoring within the European Union and neighbouring regions. The data that are integrated in the EUNIS database are collected from different sources including the European Topic Centre on Biological Diversity, the European Environment Agency and the European Environmental Information Observation Network. Datasets consist of information about: (a) species (more than 278,000 taxa occurring in Europe), (b) habitat types (e.g. marine and coastal ecosystems), and (c) sites (i.e. protected areas).

The EUNIS database can be accessed through the web-accessible EUNIS information system that supports searching for resources based on the three major types they contain. Moreover, data are also expressed in RDF/XML format to facilitate combining EUNIS data with other datasets.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

EUNIS focuses on species, habitat types and protected areas in Europe, so the collected information is geographically restricted. Moreover, it contains detailed information on specific habitats and protected areas, which is crucial for implementing ecosystem-based fisheries management, which in turn ensures that fishing practices do not harm the broader marine environment.

3.10 Aquafood Rating Schemes (e.g. WWF Common Methodology)

WWF developed three methodologies (wild capture, aquaculture, and freshwater) to assess the environmental sustainability of aquafood species from wild-capture fisheries and aquacultures. These methods form the foundation for the recommendations in WWF's various consumer aquafood guides, helping people make eco-friendly aquafood choices. For wild-capture fisheries, the methodology considers scientific data on the health of fish stocks or the species' susceptibility to fishing pressure. It also evaluates the environmental effects of the fishing gear used and assesses how well the fishery is managed to maintain ecological sustainability. For farmed species, the approach examines the use of key resources such as water, energy, and feed. It also assesses the environmental, wildlife, and community impacts of the specific aquaculture system, along with the strength and suitability of the management framework in place.

The Common Assessment Methodologies (CAM) is a tool used to assess the sustainability of aquafood based on ecological factors. It relies on publicly available fishing management reports, scientific data and research to evaluate the risk levels associated with different sources of aquafood. CAM supports WWF's efforts to restore ocean health for the benefit of people and nature by promoting responsible aquafood choices.

The basic methodologies that are provided are:

⁶¹ <https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/>

- The Marine Common Assessment Methodology focuses on marine wild-capture fisheries. It is a risk-based assessment to evaluate the impact of a fishery on fish stocks and the marine environment. It makes use of publicly available scientific data and documents and considers the most recent scientific research. It is divided into the following categories: (a) status of the target stock, (b) ecological effects of the fishery, and (c) management of the fishery.
- Freshwater Wild Capture Methodology focuses on freshwater fisheries.
- The Common Aquaculture Methodology focuses on aquaculture production systems. It is divided into three categories, namely (a) sustainable use of the resource, (b) interactions and impact, and (c) management.

An assessment is performed on a fishery defined by species, stock and gear details. For aquaculture an assessment is based on species, production method, and country. Each assessment results in an overall risk rating using a traffic light coding system: green for low risk, orange for medium risk, and red for high risk. The assessments are updated on a regular basis (wild capture typically once a year, aquaculture less frequent) by a team of consultants. The full assessments are not publicly available, but the summaries are shared through websites and consumer-facing apps and websites in various countries.

Figure 13. WWF common methodology for environmental sustainability of seafood species

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The WWF database and other rating schemes have thousands of assessments on fisheries and aquaculture. The results are used by these organisations to provide consumer information. Assessors for seafood rating schemes might be able to use data generated through the VeriFish app. (Partial) Assessment scores could be drawn from the ratings databases.

3.11 FAIR-FISH-Database

The Fair-Fish database⁶², is designed to collect, systematize and make available all welfare-related knowledge to be found on food fishes in the wild, in captivity and during catching in order to help improve fish welfare and avoid practices that harm fish. It aims to provide a consistent overview of the welfare of farmed fish, by gathering ethological knowledge categorized into profiles of farmed aquatic species. In the context of Fair-Fish, good fish welfare is guaranteed if a fish may live up to the potential of the species and develop its

⁶² <https://fair-fish-database.net/>

individuality. If, for example, a farmer lets the fishes live up to their species' potential and develop their individuality, allowing space also for positive experiences including playing, the farmer is automatically minimising pain, suffering, and stress. If, on the other hand, the farmer concentrates all efforts on reducing pain, suffering, and stress of the fishes, they will not necessarily live up to their potential. Fair-Fish adopts a combination of a function-based, feelings-based and nature-based approach to welfare, by valuing not only the freedom from injuries and stress (function-based approach) but supporting attempts to provide rewarding experiences and cognitive challenges (feelings-based approach) as well as arguing for enclosures that mimic the wild habitat as best as possible and allow for natural behaviour (nature-based approach).

Fishes are organized in the form of a species tree, into different taxonomic classes, supporting the efficient exploration. For each WelfareCheck, there is a given WelfareScore for the likelihood of the species to experience good welfare under minimal farming conditions, the potential of the species to experience good welfare under high-standard farming conditions, and the certainty about these. For each species in the species tree, the WelfareScore may vary from zero to 10 for each of these three dimensions, which are represented by the first line, the second line, and the third line, respectively. Upon the selection of a particular fish species more details about the species are given, including taxonomic information, IUCN Red List status, distribution, habitat information, common names, images, growth characteristics, swimming aspects, reproduction, social behaviour but also handling details. More details can be provided by clicking on the WelfareCheck that reveals all the collected ethological findings from the literature on the most important aspects during the life course, both biologically and concerning the habitat. For some of the species, specific advice is given with to-be-preferred farming conditions for aquaculture, or catching methods with the least threatening for this species and which changes to the gear or the catching process will potentially result in improvements of welfare.

Figure 14. Fair-Fish database sample page

At the time of writing this report, the Fair-Fish database contains WelfareChecks for 93 species (88 for farmed ones and 5 for captured fisheries).

Why is it important for VeriFish?

It contains detailed information about good fish welfare, by collecting and integrating information from several literature resources.

3.12 Bycatch Management Information System (BMIS)

Bycatch Management Information System focuses on bycatch mitigation and management in oceanic tuna and billfish fisheries using longline, purse seine and gillnets in the Pacific region. It is an open resource useful for fishery managers, fishers, scientists, observers, educators and anyone with an interest in fisheries management. As a reference and educational tool, the BMIS aims to support the adoption and implementation of science-based management measures so that bycatch is managed comprehensively and sustainably. The BMIS is concerned with highly migratory species with low reproductive rates, including seabirds, sharks and rays, sea turtles and marine mammals. For each species, detailed reference data can be found through BMIS, as well as references to other publicly available ByCatch databases (e.g. from

Commission For The Conservation of Southern Bluefin Tuna⁶³, from IATTC⁶⁴, etc.). ByCatch data can be accessed and explored through the Bycatch Data Explorer⁶⁵. The following image shows the time series regarding ByCatch of Green turtle using longlines between 2013-2022.

Figure 15. Time series of Green turtle bycatch by the Bycatch Management Information System

Why is it important for VeriFish?

Tuna and billfish fisheries are known for having a relatively high risk of bycatch or interaction with ETP species. Therefore, databases compiling this kind of information will add significant insights into the performance of fisheries. The BMIS database contains detailed information about fisheries capturing non-target species, which is important for safeguarding ETP species and preventing overfishing and stock depletion (e.g. fishes captured before maturity).

⁶³ https://www.ccsbt.org/en/userfiles/file/data/ERSWG_Data.xlsx

⁶⁴ <https://www.iattc.org/en-US/Data/Public-domain>

⁶⁵ <https://www.bmis-bycatch.org/bycatch-data-explorer-beta-version>

3.13 FishSource

FishSource⁶⁶ is a publicly available data source with profiles on fisheries. It was created and maintained by the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership (SFP) and was developed to offer major seafood buyers timely, impartial, and actionable information on these fisheries and regions. FishSource compiles and summarizes publicly available scientific and technical data about fisheries and aquaculture, presenting it in an easily interpretable format for businesses, researchers, NGOs, and other stakeholders. Its platform does not make direct sustainability judgments. Instead, it provides both qualitative and quantitative information—such as stock status, management quality, and environmental impacts—allowing users to assess sustainability according to their own standards. FishSource profiles thousands of fisheries and dozens of aquaculture regions, covering nearly 40% of global landings and about 80% of what is sold at retail in North America and Europe. FishSource is also maintaining different management score indicators, as described in the previous section. We should note that these indicators are not included in GRSF.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FishSource assigns management scores for different fisheries supporting the corresponding indicators on the governance sub-pillar.

3.14 FisheryProgress

Fishery progress is an online database tracking the progress of Fishery Improvement Programmes (FIPs) around the world. A FIP is a collaborative effort that brings together fishers, the seafood industry, scientists, NGOs, and sometimes governments. It makes tracking progress more efficient, consistent, and reliable. FisheryProgress tracks progress on environmental indicators (stock, gear impact and management) and social accountability. The Conservation Alliance for Seafood Solutions⁶⁷ developed the guidelines that are the foundation for the website.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

For fisheries that are not independently certified, but are in an improvement trajectory, it might be relevant for the market and consumers to indicate how far they are in improving sustainable performance. In the framework, this can be referred to as a reference to a status in FisheryProgress.

3.15 Other relevant sources

- Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) databases are mainly responsible for the management of tuna species and billfishes. They do have a wealth of data on fisheries statistics. For

⁶⁶ <https://www.fishsource.org/>

⁶⁷ <https://fisheryprogress.org/about-us/conservation-alliance-seafood-solutions>

example, the INTERNATIONAL CONVENTION FOR THE CONSERVATION OF ATLANTIC TUNAS has statistical data that can be accessed through the ICCAT website. The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission also has accessible statistical data. Where GRSF may not have the desired detail, they can be complemented with data from these databases.

- Certification data from Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) and Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC). MSC maintains a database of certified fisheries and assessment documents, that can be accessed through the “Track a Fishery” tool. ASC has a similar tool called “Find a Farm”, that supports retrieving responsible fish and shellfish farms.
- STECF Report on Fishery Sustainability Indicators (STECF 23-18), developed a detailed classification (with 32 fishing gears) to adequately represent the diversity of bycatch risks. In their report they contain the corresponding code with respect to ISSCFG code (from FAO), that is already integrated in GRSF.
- Seafood Carbon Emissions Tool⁶⁸ is a web-based tool that displays information on the carbon footprints of fisheries and aquaculture products and compares them to those of terrestrial protein products (beef, chicken, pork, beef, lamb and soy). can also be used as a data collection portal, and seafood producers and other data holders are encouraged to submit data on carbon emissions of their products to better inform future carbon footprint estimates.

One of the measures established under the common market organisation (CMO) are regulatory marketing standards for fishery products. In 2019, an evaluation of the implementation of the marketing standards was carried out to assess whether the existing marketing standards were still fit for purpose. The evaluation concluded amongst others that the existing marketing standards do not sufficiently contribute to a level playing field on environmental and social aspects and have not been equipped to deliver on the objective of enabling the EU market to be provided with sustainable products.

Consequently, the revision of the marketing standards was included as an initiative under the Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. The Commission engaged STECF to help with the development of robust policy options for the revision of the EU regulatory marketing standards in terms of incorporating sustainability aspects.

The main objective of STECF was to assess the identified criteria and indicators in terms of their potential to be incorporated in regulatory marketing standards, ideally for both fishery and aquaculture products (FAPs) on the EU market, independently of their origin (domestic and imports). STECF has addressed this through a series of reports focusing on criteria and indicators to incorporate sustainability aspects into seafood

⁶⁸ <http://seafoodco2.dal.ca/>

marketing standards under the CMO. These reports aimed to develop indicators suitable for implementation in semi-automated systems, leading to a tiered framework for data use and evaluation.

The STECF EWG 20-05 report, followed by EWG 22-12 and EWG 23-18, introduced two indicator levels. EWG 20-05 laid the groundwork by proposing transparent, scientifically sound, and verifiable methods for assessing sustainability aspects of fisheries and aquaculture products along the supply chain. The indicator selection for wild capture fisheries has been published in 2025 by Grati et al⁶⁹. Application of this approach in VeriFish includes Tier 1 data from publicly accessible databases including FAO Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries. The results of the work are planned to be incorporated in a web-app in 2025

4 Nutrition and Health Indicators Data Sources

The main objective of nutrition and health indicators is to underscore the vital role of aquafood in promoting human health and meeting dietary requirements, by combining data sources about the nutritional composition of aquafood products and their dietary impact on health. The following table summarizes the main data sources and their key entities, which are described in more detail in the sequel.

Table 10. Main nutrition and health data sources considered in the VeriFish framework

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level
FAO/INFOODS uFish	Nutrient value of fish	Free / Excel Database
FoodEXplorer	Protein, carbohydrate, lipids, minerals, vitamins, fatty acids of fish species	Limited / API
FoodEx2	Food Items, processes	Free / SPARQL
World Health Organization (WHO)	nutrition, food safety	Free / Reports, Glossaries, Search portals

⁶⁹ Grati, F., Druon, J.N., Gascuel, D., Absil, C., Bastardie, F., Bonanomi, S., Fabi, G., Glemarec, G., Guitton, J., Hornborg, S. and Iriondo, A., 2025. Fisheries performance indicators for assessing the ecological sustainability of wild-caught seafood products in Europe. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, p.100632.

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level
Global Nutrition Report (GNR)	Diet, nutrition	Free / Downloadable data

4.1 FAO/INFOODS Global Food Composition Database for Fish and Shellfish (uFish)

The FAO/INFOODS Global Food Composition Database for Fish and Shellfish (uFish)⁷⁰ is a comprehensive resource providing nutrient values for a wide range of fish, crustaceans, and molluscs in various forms, including raw, cooked, and processed. It is the result of the long-standing collaboration between the FAO Nutrition and Food Systems Division and the FAO Fisheries Department. The database, which can be delivered in the form of an Excel Spreadsheet, offers detailed information on key nutritional components such as proximates, minerals, vitamins, amino acids, and fatty acids. The structure of uFish is organized into 12 distinct datasheets, with datasheets 04 to 07 containing the core nutrient values. The majority of the data are derived from analytical measurements, supplemented by information from other credible sources. The data compilation process adheres to the standards and guidelines established by FAO/INFOODS, ensuring consistency, reliability, and comprehensive documentation.

The core objectives of uFish are: (a) to provide, at a global level, nutrient data (energy, macronutrients, main minerals and vitamins, amino acids and fatty acids) for various fish and shellfish species, covering different catch regions and/or origins of aquaculture production, (b) to report compositional data with comprehensive documentation following international standards and guidelines, (c) to allow compilers to include relevant nutritional values for fish and shellfish into their national or regional food composition tables or databases, (d) to increase the quality and precision of nutrient intake estimations taking variations in the composition fish and shellfish into account, and (e) to identify where compositional data are still missing.

To achieve these objectives, the following principles were applied:

- compile complete nutrient sets of fish and shellfish and report as few missing data as possible
- represent the mean composition of fish and shellfish based on available analytical data only if no or very few analytical data are found are non-analytical data from published food composition tables or databases used
- as much as available data allow, portray intra-species variation of nutrient values due to: (a) production type (wild vs. farmed), or (b) origin (country of aquaculture production or fishing zone), or (c) season (winter, summer), or (d) edible part (e.g. skin-on, skinless fillet, tail meat or leg meat)

⁷⁰ <https://aims.fao.org/news/faoinfoods-global-food-composition-database-fish-and-shellfish-data-policy>

- describe foods as precisely as the original data permit. The scientific name and the related ASFIS codes are taken as the reference points to correctly identify the different species
- be as close as possible to the exact species when estimating data. Borrowing data from other species or from a higher taxonomic rank should be done with care
- evaluate, standardize, compile and document data according to international standards.

uFish was populated stemming from two earlier FAO/INFOODS databases (i.e. FAO/INFOODS Food Composition Database for Biodiversity and the FAO/INFOODS Analytical Food Composition Database), complemented with further analytical datasets obtained through INFOODS listserv, as well as with other national reference datasets. Despite the objective of being a representative compositional database on global, regional, or national level, uFish can only represent available data of a certain quality, rather than “truly representative” compositional states of the foods presented – especially when considering that data availability per species varied significantly for the different factors affecting the nutrient composition. The uFish database can be downloaded in Excel format from https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/food_composition/documents/uFiSh1.0.xlsx

Why is it important for VeriFish?

uFish is highly relevant to the nutrition and health pillar of the framework, through its details about the nutritional value of several fish. It will be able to increase the awareness of citizens about the nutritional value of unknown fish species and facilitate stakeholders to identify nutrient-dense fish species that can be promoted through sustainable aquaculture practices.

4.2 EuroFIR - FoodEXplorer

The EuroFIR FoodEXplorer⁷¹ is a comprehensive online platform developed by EuroFIR (European Food Information Resource) to provide access to harmonized food composition data from various national food databases across Europe and beyond. The platform integrates detailed information about the nutritional content of foods, including macro- and micronutrients, bioactive compounds, and food classifications. Its primary goal is to support research, policy-making, industry applications, and consumer health initiatives by providing reliable, standardized food composition data. FoodEXplorer allows users to search data simultaneously from most EU Member States and an increasing number of countries outside Europe, as well as access to standardised value documentation. FoodEXplorer does not contain full reference datasets. Instead, there is one value for each food-component combination within each national dataset

Food resources are categorized into different Food Groups, one of them being Seafood. Given a seafood resource various details are then given described in terms of food attributes (i.e. edible portion, serving size,

⁷¹ <https://www.eurofir.org/our-tools/foodexplorer/>

fatty acids conversion factor, pH, solids, etc.), food components (i.e. energy, protein, carbohydrate components, lipid components, minerals, vitamins, fatty acids, etc.), and links with external data sources (i.e. Languag and FoodEx2 codes). FoodExplorer can be accessed either through the dedicated search portal from EuroFIR⁷², or through their API⁷³. The API supports searching FoodExplorer databases using REST or SOAP services, and results are delivered in structured formats (e.g. XML, JSON). Accessing the API is restricted for registered users.

Nutritional composition data, including macro and micronutrients, were compiled for over 70 fish species from 39 food composition databases (FCDBs) accessible via EuroFIR's FoodExplorer tool. This dataset, initially developed under the SEAFOODTOMORROW project in 2018⁷⁴, was expanded to incorporate updated data, broader geographic and more detailed fatty acid composition. The dataset includes fish in raw, cooked, and processed forms. Nutrient values were harmonised through standardisation of units and formatting, along with terminological alignment to ensure consistency across FCDBs. Outliers were identified using interquartile range (IQR) thresholds and subsequently reviewed by nutrition experts for plausibility based on literature and domain knowledge. Following harmonisation, averages were calculated per nutrient and fish type. In cases where FCDBs filled missing data by borrowing values from other databases, leading to duplication across sources, these values were identified and accounted for only once in the averaging process to prevent overrepresentation. Due to differences in how fish are reported across FCDBs, ranging from species-level names to generic commercial terms, nutrient data were aggregated under generic fish names (e.g., "Salmon, raw") to retain all relevant entries.

⁷² https://www.eurofir.org/FoodExplorer/search_results.php

⁷³ <https://eurofir.org/FoodExplorer/API/>

⁷⁴ DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7825958; GA No. 773400

Figure 16. FoodExplorer resources filtered via the EuroFIR portal

The following figure demonstrates part of the results of GetFoodNutVal, that retrieves the nutritive value of the food item with code “0032383”, which is salmon. The illustrated results demonstrate the carbohydrate values and the total fat.

FoodExplorer / GetFoodAll

GET

Params • Authorization Headers (11) Body Scripts Settings

Query Params

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Key	Value
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> query	GetFoodNutVal
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> param	0032383

Body Cookies (1) Headers (16) Test Results 200 O

```
{
  "Response": [
    {
      "no": 0,
      "country": "LV",
      "foodid": "0032383",
      "componentid": "",
      "componentCode": "CHO",
      "selectedValue": "21.4",
      "comp_name": "carbohydrate",
      "compgr_name": "CARBOHYDRATE COMPONENTS",
      "unit": "g",
      "matrix": "W",
      "valueType": "BE",
      "accType": "X",
      "methodType": "X",
      "methodIndicator": "MIR003",
      "refType": "X",
      "refaccType": "X",
      "citation": ""
    },
    {
      "no": 1,
      "country": "LV",
      "foodid": "0032383",
      "componentid": "",
      "componentCode": "FAT",
      "selectedValue": "13.9",
      "comp_name": "fat, total",
      "compgr_name": "LIPID COMPONENTS",
      "unit": "g",
      "matrix": "W",
      "valueType": "BE"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 17. Sample results from GetFoodNutVal on nutritive value of salmon

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FoodExplorer provides access to a wealth of information regarding the nutrient composition data for various seafood species, supporting the evaluation of seafood contribution to dietary health while encouraging consumption choices.

4.3 FoodEx2

FoodEx2 is a food classification and description system developed by EFSA to serve as a harmonization tool for collecting and analysing data across EU Member States. The system is a combination of classifications and

descriptions, including a number of hierarchies for different domains and a multitude of core terms and facets. The large number of individual food items are aggregated into food groups and broader food categories in a hierarchical parent-child relationship. Central to the system is a core list of food items or generic food descriptions that represent the minimum level of detail needed for intake or exposure assessments. More detailed terms can be found on the “extended list”. A parent-child relationship exists between a core list food item and its related extended list food items. The terms of the core and extended list may be aggregated in different ways according to the needs of the different food safety domains. The current version has seven hierarchies: five domain-specific and a general purpose one available for the users, and a service hierarchy for the management of the terminology. Facets are used to add further detail to the information provided by the food list term. Facets are collections of additional terms describing properties and aspects of foods from various perspectives.

FoodEx2 can be accessed through the dedicated application called Catalogue Browser⁷⁵ as well as in structured format through its transformed version into a SKOS thesaurus⁷⁶. We should also note, that FoodEx2 codes are also available through EuroFIR’s FoodEXplorer.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FoodEx2 is a valuable source since apart from listing seafood resources as food items it also describes the related processes that are (or can be) applied to them. Facets provide extra details about food items, such as processing, preservation, ingredients, etc.

4.4 World Health Organization (WHO) data collections

The World Health Organization (WHO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for international public health. WHO works to promote global health, ensuring universal health coverage, and safeguarding populations from health emergencies. Its mission is to ensure that all people can attain the highest possible level of health, which it achieves through leadership in global health matters, setting norms and standards, providing technical support to countries, and monitoring and assessing health trends. The WHO addresses a wide range of health issues, including infectious diseases, non-communicable diseases, mental health, environmental health, and health systems strengthening. It also plays a critical role in responding to global health emergencies, such as pandemics and humanitarian crises.

WHO maintains extensive data collections that are critical for global health monitoring, research and policy-making. These collections cover a broad spectrum of health-related domains, including nutrition, food safety, and environmental health. The most prominent ones that are related to the purposes of the framework are:

⁷⁵ <https://github.com/openefsa/catalogue-browser>

⁷⁶ Marketakis, Y., Kritsotaki, A., Axaridou, A., Fafalios, P., Mountantonakis, M. and Tzitzikas, Y., 2024. *On Transforming FoodEx2 to a Standardized and Interoperable Thesaurus*.

- **Glossary of health data, statistics and public health indicators**⁷⁷, which is the standard set of terminology for health data and indicators.
- **Micronutrients database**⁷⁸, providing access to the macronutrient status of populations at the national level.
- **Nutrition Landscape Information System (NLIS)**⁷⁹, providing access to nutrition and nutrition-related health and development data
- **Vitamin and Mineral Nutrition Information System (VMNIS)**⁸⁰, which collects and summarizes data on vitamin and mineral status of populations.
- **Food Safety Collaborative Platform**⁸¹, which aggregates data from various sources to provide health-based guidance values for different food chemicals and further information on dietary exposure risk assessment.
- **Global database on the Implementation of Food and Nutrition Action (GIFNA)**⁸², providing valuable information on the implementation of numerous nutrition policies and interventions.
- **International Peer Reviewed Chemical Safety Information (INCHEM)**⁸³, that includes all types of chemicals from the full range of exposure situations, including food.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

Data collections from WHO, offer essential insights into the nutritional (i.e. by identifying species with high nutritional value, by considering regional variations in nutritional intake to assess where aquafood consumption could improve population health, etc.) and health-related (i.e. identify health risks from pollutants and contaminants in aquafood) dimensions of the framework.

4.5 Global Nutrition Report (GNR)

The Global Nutrition Report (GNR)⁸⁴ is the world's leading independent assessment of the state of global nutrition. It serves as a critical resource for understanding the challenges and progress related to malnutrition worldwide. The GNR provides the best available data, in-depth analysis, and evidence-based expert opinions to drive action on nutrition where it is most urgently needed. Its primary purpose is to act as an accountability mechanism, tracking progress toward global nutrition targets and the commitments made to achieve them. Despite generating global annual nutrition reports, it also supports accessing the latest data

⁷⁷ <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240105485>

⁷⁸ <https://platform.who.int/nutrition/micronutrients-database>

⁷⁹ <https://www.who.int/teams/nutrition-and-food-safety/databases/nutrition-landscape-information-system>

⁸⁰ <https://www.who.int/teams/nutrition-and-food-safety/databases/vitamin-and-mineral-nutrition-information-system>

⁸¹ <https://apps.who.int/foscollab/>

⁸² <https://gifna.who.int/>

⁸³ <https://www.inchem.org/>

⁸⁴ <https://globalnutritionreport.org/>

on nutrition at global, regional and country level. Such resources bring together the latest data on diet, the burden of malnutrition, nutrition strategies and financing, social determinants of nutrition and environmental impacts to comprehensively assess the state of global nutrition.

The Global Nutrition Report's Country Nutrition Profiles capture the state of nutrition and progress towards the global nutrition targets at the country, regional and global level. They bring together the latest data on child and adult diet and burden of malnutrition, as well as nutrition strategies and financing and social determinants of nutrition. They help key stakeholders inform and implement evidence-based nutrition policies by offering them in-depth insights into the status of malnutrition in countries around the globe and allowing them to make comparisons at the subregional, regional and global level.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

GNR provides evidence on diet and the burden of malnutrition for several countries. By exploiting the wealth of data on different countries, stakeholders can identify nutrition and health needs and further promote sustainably sourced aquafood that can help fill such micronutrient gaps. Moreover, they can be used to develop target policy recommendations (for example promote aquafood as a healthier alternative if red meat consumption is high).

5 Social and Economic Indicators Data Sources

The social and economic indicators in this project will be designed to provide consumers with meaningful insights and raise awareness about the broader social and economic dimensions related to the sustainability narrative of aquafoods. They will be based on widely recognized data sources, including international conventions, official lists, and reports covering key social, ethical and economic issues in supply chains. The goal is to develop a practical framework that can be applied to both farmed (AQ) and wild-caught (WC) aquafoods. Some data sources, such as those specific to fishing vessels, will be relevant only to the fisheries sector. These data sources will be further explored and tested before being finally included in the project. The following table presents a set of key data sources (described in detail in subsequent sections). These sources are still under review and have not been finalized. They are intended to support the creation of risk-based indicators, estimating the likelihood of social and economic concerns being present. However, these indicators will not provide a precise picture of conditions for specific aquafood products.

Table 11. Key social and economic data sources considered in the VeriFish framework

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level	Sector
Ratification of ILO Conventions - various	work rights, child labour, working condition, workers safety, workers training and certification etc.	Public	AQ/WC but some only relevant for WC
Global Slavery Index	forced labour & modern slavery	Public	AQ/WC
Transparency International	corruption	Public	AQ/WC
EU Data Collection Framework (DCF) ⁸⁵	employment data, vessel and fleet economics, aquaculture economic variables	Public	AQ/WC
European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA) ⁸⁶	sales data (e.g. prices), data on jobs in processing, fishing and aquaculture	Public	AQ/WC
EMODNET Human Activities data sets	fishing effort, fishing intensity, fish sales	Public	AQ/WC
Trafficking in persons report	global assessment of the country-level trends in forced labour & human trafficking	Public	AQ/WC
IUU Vessel Lists (this might be more appropriate as tier 2)	illegal, unreported & unregulated fishing activity (intrinsically linked to human rights abuses)	Public	WC
Flags of Convenience Lists	avoidance of taxes, cheap, lower safety & social regulations, low	Public	WC

⁸⁵ It covers various social and economic characteristics of fisheries (e.g. profitability, employment, costs, and revenue of the fishing and aquaculture sectors)

⁸⁶ includes entities like market prices, trade data, and financial statistics related to fisheries and aquaculture

Data Source	Main entities	Access Level	Sector
	transparency, associated with criminal activity & substandard working conditions		
Port States Measures Agreement	stricter port controls on foreign fleets to eliminate IUU fish - associated with bad labour practices	Public	WC
Subsidies for fishing vessels - various	Neg: can lead to overfishing & impact on stocks, in DWF forced labour Pos: income support to vessels & communities, modernization, support research	Public	WC
IMO STCW-F ratification	international standards for training, certification & watchkeeping, improving safety at sea	Public	WC
Provision of data to the global record	fleet management	Public	WC
FishStatJ	country level - production value, first sale value of landings. import export volume & values	Public	AQ/WC

5.1 ILO Conventions

The International Labour Organizations (ILO)⁸⁷ is devoted to promoting social justice and internationally recognized human and labour rights, pursuing its founding mission that social justice is essential to universal and lasting peace. ILO conventions set the minimum standard for labour rights, working conditions and social protections to ensure fair and decent work worldwide. They are legally binding international treaties that set global labour standards to ensure fair and decent work conditions. Once ratified, they require countries to align their national laws with the convention's provisions. They establish international norms on issues such as child labour, forced labour, workplace safety, working hours, and collective bargaining. The ILO monitors

⁸⁷ <https://www.ilo.org/>

compliance through reporting mechanisms and expert reviews, promoting accountability. While countries voluntarily choose which conventions to ratify, the standards often influence national policies even without formal adoption. The conventions provide flexibility to accommodate different legal and economic contexts, making them a cornerstone of international labour rights.

There are several fundamental ILO conventions, such as Forced Labour Convention (1930), Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organize Convention (1948), and Minimum Age Convention (1973), that should be included in the framework. In addition, there are other conventions that are specifically related to fisheries and aquaculture (/agriculture). The list of conventions that have therefore been included here for consideration are:

- No 029 - Forced Labour Convention (1930)
- No 087 - Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise Convention (1948)
- No 105 - Abolition of Forced Labour Convention (1957)
- No 111 - Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention (1958)
- No 112 - Minimum Age (Fishermen) Convention (1959), prohibits child labour in fishing
- No 113 - Medical Examination (Fishermen) Convention (1959), ensures health of fishers, by mandating pre-employment and periodic medical examinations.
- No 114 - Fishermen's Articles of Agreement Convention (1959), ensures written and signed agreements are made between fishers and vessel owners and specifies the actual terms of employment, wages and working conditions.
- No 125 - Fishermen's Competency Certificates Convention (1966), establishes the standards for the training and certification of fishers to ensure safety at sea.
- No 126 - Accommodation of Crews (Fishermen) Convention (1966), describes the minimum standards for living conditions on fishing vessels.
- No 138 - Minimum Age Convention (1973)
- No 155 - Occupational Safety and Health Convention (1981)
- No 169 - Indigenous and tribal peoples Convention (1989)
- No 182 - Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention (1999)
- No 184 - Safety and Health in Agriculture (2001)
- No 188 - Work in Fishing Convention (2007), which establishes the minimum standards for working conditions on fishing vessels.

Ratification of an ILO Convention is the formal process by which a member country of ILO legally commits to implementing the provisions of that convention. Once a country ratifies a convention, it is obligated to align its national laws, policies, and practices with the convention's requirements and to report regularly to the ILO on its implementation. Through ratification, ILO helps improve labour rights, workplace safety and social protections influencing both national policies and international trade relationships. Finally, ILO provides a wealth of information on labour statistics through ILOSTAT⁸⁸.

⁸⁸ <https://ilostat.ilo.org/>

Why is it important for VeriFish?

ILO conventions (and ratifications) can strengthen the social and economic indicators by providing measurable, internationally recognized benchmarks on labour conditions, work rights and fair wages and contracts. Just indicatively, one of the most fundamental conventions, No 029 - Forced Labour Convention (1930), has been ratified from 181 countries worldwide⁸⁹. More detailed about the ratifications per country or per convention can be found from NORMLEX, the information system of ILO.

5.2 Global Slavery Index

The Global Slavery Index (GSI)⁹⁰ is a global annual report published by the Walk Free Foundation that quantifies modern slavery worldwide. The index provides a country-by-country assessment of the prevalence, drivers, and government responses to modern slavery, including forced labour, human trafficking, debt bondage, and forced marriage. The main objectives of GSI are to: (a) measure prevalence by estimating the number of people living in modern slavery in each country (this covers forced labour), (b) evaluate government responses and actions to criminalize modern slavery, protect victims, etc. (c) identify key drivers and risk factors that increase modern slavery, and (d) raise public awareness. The key metrics of GSI are: (a) prevalence score, (b) vulnerability score, and (c) government response tier.

Information from the GSI can be previewed in the form of annual reports that summarize the main findings, as well as through detailed datasets that can be explored directly from GSI web portal, or offline as spreadsheet data, offering raw data on prevalence, vulnerability factors and government responses that can be filtered by country, year or indicator for deeper analysis.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

GSI provide details about the fishing industry which has a high risk of modern slavery.

5.3 Transparency International

Transparency International (TI) is a global non-governmental organization, with the mission to combat corruption and promote transparency, accountability, and integrity across all sectors of society. It operates through a network of over 100 national chapters worldwide, addressing corruption at local, national, and international levels. TI collaborates with governments, businesses and civil society to expose corrupt systems. They produce reports like the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) which ranks countries by perceived public-sector corruption. CPI is a composite indicator produced by aggregating data from various external surveys and assessments (from World Bank, World Economic Forum and others).

Why is it important for VeriFish?

⁸⁹ https://normlex.ilo.org/dyn/nrmlx_en/f?p=1000:11300:0::NO:11300:P11300_INSTRUMENT_ID:312174

⁹⁰ <https://www.walkfree.org/global-slavery-index/>

TI can be used to alert for weak fisheries management, or illegal fishing because of corruption in the public sector (e.g. bribery of officials).

5.4 Data Collection Framework (DCF)

The EU Data Collection Framework (DCF) considers the collection of various social and economic data on fisheries and aquaculture. More specifically, it mandates that all member states are obliged to gather data related to: (a) employment (e.g. number of worker, full-time vs part-time employment), (b) fleet economics (e.g. costs, revenues, profit), (c) vessel characteristics (e.g. size, engine power, gear type), and (d) aquaculture economic variables (production costs, sales data).

Why is it important for VeriFish?

DCF provides the basic data about the social and economic characteristics in the domain of fisheries and aquaculture.

5.5 European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products

The European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA)⁹¹ is an initiative by the European Commission aimed at improving market transparency and efficiency in the fisheries and aquaculture sector. It provides up-to-date, harmonized, and detailed data on the production, trade, processing, and consumption of aquafood products across the EU and international markets. The data covers various stages of the supply chain, from first sale (landing prices) to retail markets, enabling stakeholders to analyze trends, price fluctuations, and supply-demand dynamics. Some of the main entities that fall within the environmental indicators are product categories and consumption patterns.

While the majority of data is publicly available through the EUMOFA platform, some detailed or proprietary information may be restricted to protect the interests of individual businesses or comply with various regulations. They can be accessed through the web-accessible platform that also provides various tools to visualize data. Certain datasets and reports are also available for download in structured formats like Excel and CSV.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

EUMOFA contains detailed information on market data, employment and labour trends. These resources support the provision of detailed economic variables.

5.6 EMODnet Human Activities

EMODnet Human Activities⁹² aims to facilitate access to existing marine data on activities carried out in EU waters, by building a single entry point for geographic information on 20 different themes. The main

⁹¹ <https://eumofa.eu/>

⁹² <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities>

objective of EMODnet Human Activities is to make available information on the geographical position, spatial extent and attributes of a wide array of marine and maritime human activities throughout Europe. Particular attention is given to providing, when possible, historical time series to indicate the temporal variation of activities such as fishing, shipping density and port traffic.

The data products are organized into different themes, such as Fisheries, Aquaculture, Energy, Waste Disposal, Shipping Density, and others. Regarding aquaculture the activities that are described focus on the production of finfish, shellfish and freshwater fish, describing the actual geographic region, in terms of points, and other attributes such as tonnage per year for each species. Regarding fisheries, the activities revolve around fisheries zones, fish catches, fishing effort, fishing intensity and fish sales.

Resources from EMODnet Human Activities can be accessed in a similar manner, as other EMODnet resources (e.g. EMODnet Biology data); through a Map Viewer, and through browsing and searching over the products catalogue.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

It provides detailed data covering various related aspects such as fishing effort, fish sales about fisheries, etc.

5.7 The Trafficking in Persons Report

The Trafficking in Persons (TIP) Report⁹³ is an annual publication by the U.S. Department of State that evaluates global efforts to combat human trafficking. It ranks countries into three tiers based on their level of compliance with the minimum standards for the elimination of trafficking, as defined in the U.S. Trafficking Victims Protection Act (TVPA). The report includes both narrative assessments and a tier ranking system, taking into account the extent of government efforts to prosecute traffickers, protect victims, and prevent trafficking. The three tiers are:

- Tier 1: Countries whose governments fully meet the TVPA's minimum standards.
- Tier 2: Countries that do not fully meet the standards but are making significant efforts to bring themselves into compliance.
- Tier 3: Countries whose governments do not fully meet the standards and are not making significant efforts to do so.

The TIP Report provides both qualitative and comparative insights, offering a consistent, internationally recognized benchmark for evaluating trafficking risks at the country level.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

⁹³ <https://www.state.gov/reports-office-to-monitor-and-combat-trafficking-in-persons/>

The TIP Report is a valuable source for assessing the risk of human trafficking in aquafood-producing countries. It enables the VeriFish framework to incorporate a standardized, high-level risk indicator for labour exploitation and forced labour in the supply chain. Though it operates at the national level, it offers important context for identifying high-risk sourcing regions, supporting risk-based assessments in the absence of traceable, site-level data.

5.8 Official 'IUU' Vessel Lists

Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing vessel lists⁹⁴ are maintained by Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs) and provide publicly accessible information on vessels that have been identified as engaging in IUU fishing activities. These lists are compiled based on evidence of violations such as fishing without authorization, misreporting catches, using prohibited gear, or fishing in closed areas. Each RFMO has its own process and criteria for listing vessels, often following investigation and consultation with the flag State. Once listed, vessels may face sanctions including port denials, trade restrictions, and increased inspections. Lists are regularly updated and may include vessel name, flag, identification numbers, owner/operator, and details of the IUU activities. There are currently several IUU vessel lists maintained by major RFMOs, including:

- ICCAT (International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas)
- IOTC (Indian Ocean Tuna Commission)
- NEAFC (North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission)
- SEAFO, NAFO, CCAMLR, and others

IUU lists can be browsed and searched directly from their website using various criteria such as vessel name, flags, owner, etc. and allows customizing search by applying different filters (e.g. exclude vessel lists by particular RFMOs). In addition, the list can be download as an Excel file⁹⁵.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

These lists are a direct and credible source of information on high-risk vessels operating outside regulatory frameworks. They offer a mechanism to screen out known offenders from supply chains and provide an evidence-based tool to support the “verifiable” and “legitimate” sourcing criteria within the framework. Although they do not capture all IUU activity, their official and public nature makes them a strong compliance-linked data source for assessing risk at the vessel level.

⁹⁴ <https://www.iuu-vessels.org/>

⁹⁵ <https://www.iuu-vessels.org/Home/Download>

5.9 Flags of Convenience Lists

Flags of Convenience (FoC) refer to the practice of vessel owners registering ships in countries other than their own to take advantage of more lenient regulations, lower fees, or reduced oversight. These registries are often criticized for providing limited transparency and weak enforcement of labour, safety, and environmental standards. Several organizations and research institutions have compiled FoC lists to identify countries that offer open registries with insufficient controls over the vessels they flag. A notable source is the International Transport Workers' Federation (ITF)⁹⁶, which maintains a long-standing and recognized FoC list, based on criteria including:

- Lack of genuine link between the vessel owner and the flag State
- Weak enforcement of international labour conventions
- Low transparency and oversight of vessel operations
- History of association with labour abuses, IUU fishing, or poor safety records

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FoC lists provide a risk indicator at the flag State level, relevant to both social and environmental aspects of fisheries. A flag associated with FoC practices may signal weaker governance, increasing the risk of labour violations, IUU activity, and lack of accountability. Incorporating FoC status into the VeriFish framework supports risk-based screening of vessel sourcing and helps to flag potential issues where traceability to a high-standard flag State is absent.

5.10 Port State Measures Agreement

The Port State Measures Agreement (PSMA)⁹⁷ is a binding international treaty adopted by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) to prevent, deter, and eliminate Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing by strengthening port controls. It sets minimum standards for port States to inspect foreign-flagged vessels when they enter ports, deny access to those suspected of IUU fishing, and share information among parties to enhance transparency. The PSMA came into force in 2016 and is the first international treaty to specifically target IUU fishing. It applies to any use of ports for landing, transshipment, packaging, or processing of fish and includes obligations such as:

- Pre-arrival notifications and documentation
- Inspections of fishing vessels
- Denial of port entry or use when IUU activity is suspected

⁹⁶ <https://www.itfseafarers.org/en/issues/flags-of-convenience/current-registries-listed-focs>

⁹⁷ <https://www.fao.org/port-state-measures/en/>

- Reporting of inspection outcomes to flag States and relevant RFMOs

A country's participation in the PSMA - as well as its implementation capacity - can be an important signal of its commitment to responsible fisheries governance.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The PSMA is a governance indicator that reflects a country's active role in preventing IUU fishing through port-level enforcement. Countries that are parties to the PSMA and are effectively implementing its provisions reduce the risk that IUU-caught fish enter global supply chains. This makes it a valuable criterion in the VeriFish framework for assessing the legitimacy and oversight capacity of port States involved in wild-capture fisheries.

5.11 Subsidies for Fishing Vessels

Subsidies in the fisheries sector refer to financial support provided by governments to fishing vessel operators, fishers, or related industries. These subsidies can take many forms, including fuel tax exemptions, income support, vessel construction or modernization grants, and research funding. While some subsidies aim to support coastal communities and sustainable development, others can contribute to unsustainable practices, such as overcapacity and overfishing, especially in distant water fleets (DWFs). The World Trade Organization (WTO) and institutions like the OECD have highlighted the need to differentiate between:

- Beneficial subsidies (e.g., support for research, safety, and sustainability initiatives)
- Ambiguous subsidies (e.g., capacity-neutral investments)
- Harmful subsidies (e.g., fuel support that encourages overfishing or distant water operations in already stressed fisheries)

In some cases, harmful subsidies have been linked to negative social outcomes, including labour abuses and forced labour aboard vessels operating under low-cost, low-regulation conditions.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

Subsidies are a key economic and social indicator within the aquafood supply chain. Understanding the type and intent of subsidies in place helps to assess whether a fleet or fishery is economically dependent on harmful practices, or whether subsidies are being used to foster sustainable and socially responsible outcomes. For the framework, a review of both positive and negative subsidy regimes will allow us to accurately score the economic viability, equity, and potential social risks within aquafood supply chains.

5.12 IMO STCW-F Ratification

The International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Fishing Vessel Personnel (STCW-F)⁹⁸ was adopted by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) in 1995 and entered into force in 2012. It is the first global instrument to establish mandatory minimum standards for the training and certification of crews on fishing vessels of 24 metres in length and above, or equivalent in gross tonnage. The STCW-F Convention sets out requirements related to:

- Basic safety training
- Watchkeeping duties
- Navigational safety
- Engine room operations
- Medical first aid and survival skills

Unlike merchant shipping, the fishing sector has long operated with less rigorous global oversight, making the STCW-F a crucial tool to enhance crew safety and competence- especially given the sector’s high rates of occupational accidents and fatalities.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

Ratification of the STCW-F Convention by a flag State signals a commitment to improving working and safety conditions on board fishing vessels. For the VeriFish social responsibility indicators, the ratification and implementation of STCW-F is a governance signal that helps assess the likelihood of safe, fair, and legally compliant labour conditions in fisheries. Where countries have not ratified or implemented the STCW-F, there may be a greater risk of inadequate crew training, unsafe working conditions, and weaker enforcement of labour standards.

5.13 The Global Record of Fishing Vessels, Refrigerated Transport Vessels and Supply Vessels (Global Record)

The Global Record of Fishing Vessels, Refrigerated Transport Vessels and Supply Vessels (Global Record)⁹⁹ is a voluntary initiative coordinated by the FAO to improve transparency and traceability in the fisheries sector by compiling and disseminating certified information on vessels engaged in fishing and fishing-related activities. It acts as an international platform providing reliable and up-to-date data on vessel identity, ownership, flag history, authorizations, and compliance records, including links to IUU lists and RFMO registers. Countries are encouraged to submit data for vessels above a certain size threshold, particularly those operating in waters beyond national jurisdiction. The initiative is closely tied to the implementation of international instruments

⁹⁸ <https://www.imo.org/en/ourwork/humanelement/pages/stcw-f-convention.aspx>

⁹⁹ <https://www.fao.org/global-record/en/>

such as the Port State Measures Agreement and supports efforts to combat IUU fishing by enabling cross-checks of vessel information. Data can be accessed through a dedicated Information System.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

The provision of vessel data to the Global Record is a strong indicator of transparency and state-level commitment to responsible fisheries governance. It can help verify flag state controls, support traceability, and reveal compliance history, which can be relevant when evaluating social and economic risk indicators related to vessel operations.

5.14 FishStatJ

FishStatJ¹⁰⁰ is a software tool developed by the FAO for accessing, analyzing, and visualizing global fishery and aquaculture statistics. It provides standardized time-series data on a wide range of topics, including fish production (by country, species, and environment), trade, fleet composition, and consumption. The tool allows users to download and manipulate datasets for national and regional comparisons and to track trends over time. The data originates from national submissions to the FAO, and while coverage and accuracy can vary between countries, it is one of the most comprehensive publicly available sources for global aquafood production and trade data.

Why is it important for VeriFish?

FishStatJ supports high-level economic analysis of aquaculture and fisheries trends, enabling insight into production levels, national dependency on certain fisheries, and trade patterns. These indicators can help inform risk assessments under the social and economic pillar by providing context on country-level reliance, market exposure, and fleet characteristics.

6 Indicator Framework Matrix

This section bridges the gap between theory and practice by aligning the identified data sources with the indicators of the framework. Building on the inventory of data sources carried out in Section 3, 4, and 5, we clarify how each source contributes to developing an framework across its pillars. The details are given in the following tables. More specifically, two tables are provided; one for capture fisheries indicators and one for the aquaculture indicators. For the case of indicators of the Nutrition and Health pillar, this is not required,

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/statistics/software/fishstati>

since the data sources that are identified are not many and they can be developed using resources from the most prominent ones (e.i. EuroFIR FoodEXplorer and uFish). Moreover, for the case of socio-economic indicators a table is not provided because of the vague descriptions of this pillar. Nevertheless, the corresponding data sources that are described in Section 5, are adequate for the socio-economic part.

Ideally, we should include a matrix having as rows the different indicators, and as columns the contributing data sources. However, based on the big number of both dimensions that would require the addition of big tables. To improve the readability of the report we provide a simpler visualization that contains as rows the indicators and in a second column all the data sources using their acronyms (were applicable).

The following matrix demonstrates the data sources that are contributing to capture fisheries indicators.

Table 12. Matrix of capture fisheries indicators and data sources

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Stock Status	GRSF, FishBase, SeaLifeBase, FishSource
Fishing Mortality	GRSF, FishSource
Resilience	FishBase
CO2(eq) footprint	Seafood Carbon Emissions Tool
Habitat impact	EMODnet biology, SeaAroundUs, EUNIS
Trophic effects	EMODnet Biology
ByCatch	BMIS, GRSF
ETP impact	IUCN, EUNIS, CITES, CMS, STECF (EWG 23-18)
Gear loss	Rely mostly on Tier-2 data
Capture OWI	Fair-Fish
Handling OWI	Fair-Fish
Stunning and killing	Fair-Fish
Monitoring Plan	GRSF

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Stock Management	GRSF, DCF
ETP Impact Mitigation	IUCN, CMS, CITES
Discards Mitigation	BMIS
Regulatory Framework	WISE-Marine
IUU	IUU vessel lists
Certification	GRSF, FishSource, FisheryProgress
Fisheries Improve Programme	GRSF, FishSource

The following matrix demonstrates the data sources that can be used for the aquaculture indicators.

Table 13. Matrix of aquaculture indicators and data sources

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Stunning	Fair-Fish
Maximum Stocking Density	Fair-Fish
GHG potential	EUNIS, Fair-Fish, EU MSFD
Habitat alteration for site	EUNIS, IUCN, EU MSFD, EMODnet Biology
Escape potential	EUNIS
Freshwater use	N/A (rely on Tier2 data)
Food conversion ratio	N/A (rely on Tier2 data)
Effluents released externally	EU MSFD

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Survival rate	Fair-Fish
Eye stalk ablation used	Fair-Fish
Antimicrobial therapeutic treatments used	N/A (rely on Tier2 data)
Use of GMO feed materials	N/A (rely on Tier2 data)
Robust EIA required	EUNIS
Circularity	EU MSFD

In the context of the nutrition and health pillar for aquafood, nutrient composition data can be used to inform selected indicators, and these translated into a combined nutritional quality value, and – ultimately – a score presented in the various media products and VeriFish app. Based on D2.1, key nutrient indicators identified for the VeriFish framework include protein, omega-3 fatty acids (EPA and DHA), micronutrients (e.g., selenium, iodine, vitamin D, vitamin B12), and sodium. These indicators can be populated using data from – for example – FoodEXplorer (SEAFOODTOMORROW expanded dataset), FAO uFish and AnFood/BioFoodComp (allowing for shared data across these sources), FishNutrients (FishBase), SeaFoodData (IMR), and AFCD (Harvard). All nutrient values are reported per 100g edible portion, with some consideration of product form (e.g., raw fillet), species, production method, and processing state.

To produce a balanced and fair combined nutritional value, the following structured method is proposed:

- A. Nutrient selection: Indicators are chosen based on public health relevance and availability across species. “Positive nutrients” (e.g., protein, omega-3, micronutrients) and “limiting nutrients” (e.g., sodium, saturated fat) can both be included.
- B. Reference-based values: Each nutrient is counted using % of the recommended daily intake per 100g edible portion, e.g., $\geq 100\%$ of (nutrient reference value) $NRV = 5$, $80-99\% = 4$, $60-79\% = 3$, $40-59\% = 2$, $20-39\% = 1$, and $<20\% = 0$. For limiting nutrients, the scale can be inverted (i.e., less is better).
- C. Weighting and aggregation: Each nutrient NRV-value is optionally weighted to reflect its importance in aquafood (e.g., protein and micronutrients might be weighted more heavily than omega-3s [to allow for the benefits of lean fish] or salt weighted as more detrimental). Weighted scores are summed or averaged to produce a combined nutritional quality value on a 0–5 scale.

- D. Normalisation and output: The final value can be represented as a simple score or translated into a traffic light (green–yellow–red) or star rating for consumer-facing applications. Crucially, the method caps the influence of any single nutrient (e.g., EPA/DHA), ensuring that lean, micronutrient-rich species are not undervalued

NutriScore¹⁰¹ is a widely used front-of-pack labelling system based on a nutrient profiling model developed in France. It scores foods from A (dark green, healthiest) to E (red, least healthy), based on both positive and negative nutrients (i.e., negative points: energy, total sugars, saturated fat, sodium | positive points: protein, fibre, percentage of fruits/vegetables/nuts/oils). However, NutriScore was not designed for aquafood: it was developed primarily for processed foods and lacks specific adjustments for animal-source protein quality or bioavailable micronutrients. It does not account for omega-3 fatty acids, for example, or micronutrients, such as selenium or iodine. Potentially, NutriScore could penalise oily fish (e.g. mackerel, salmon) for higher fat content without fully recognising the value of long-chain omega-3s. It is also data dependent, requiring complete datasets for all scoring components, which might not exist for less-studied aquatic species

In contrast, the proposed approach for VeriFish uses aquafood-relevant nutrient indicators aligned with dietary guidelines and health claims, emphasises nutrient density and micronutrient richness, allows transparent weighting and benchmarking specific to aquatic foods, and is adaptable across species and data contexts (including limited datasets). Calculation of a combined nutritional quality value in VeriFish must reflect the unique nutritional contributions of aquafood products, while accommodating variation in data quality and availability. The proposed approach builds on transparent, reference-based scoring and is specifically tailored to aquatic foods—unlike broader food profiling systems such as Nutri-Score. Future work to ensure a robust approach will require expert consultations to refine nutrient weights and scoring thresholds, sensitivity testing of the model across different aquafood types and data sources, and exploration of hybrid models incorporating nutrient density per kcal or g protein. Regardless, this proposed approach ensures that all aquafood types—from oily fish rich in omega-3 to lean, micronutrient-dense species—can be fairly communicated within the VeriFish system.

Regarding the Social and Economic Indicators, the following table summarizes them and provides indicative data sources that can contribute.

Table 14. Matrix of social and economic indicators and data sources

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Not on an IUU fishing list	IUU Vessel Lists, RFMO data

¹⁰¹ <https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/en/nutri-score>

Indicator	Data Source(-s)
Not considered to be a Flag of Convenience	Flags of Convenience lists
Corruption	Transparency International
Subsidies: harmful vs. supportive	Subsidies of fishing vessels, Fisheries subsidies (OECD, WTO)
Port State Controls	Port State Measures
Wages and working conditions	ILO Conventions, ITUC Global Rights index
Workers' rights and union representation	ILO Conventions, ITUC Global Rights index
Prevention of child labour	ILO Conventions
Prevention of forced labour, modern slavery & human trafficking	ILO Conventions, Global Slavery Index, Trafficking in Persons
Access to healthcare and medical facilities	ILO Conventions
Occupational Health & Safety at work	ILO Conventions
Work place training	ILO Conventions
Equality & prevention of discrimination	ILO Conventions
Respect for indigenous peoples	ILO Conventions

7 Conclusions

This deliverable has advanced the work initiated in D2.1 where the building blocks of the VeriFish Indicator Framework have been identified. The framework consists of different indicators categorised into three main pillars of indicators; 1) environmental, 2) nutrition and health, and 3) social and economic. In this deliverable we have been able to further refine, justify and document our suggested set of data sources which will be essential to develop and implement the framework. In addition, we have provided insights into their scope, key entities, accessibility and applicability. Moreover, the mapping of data sources to individual indicators has served as a critical step toward operationalizing the framework which will deliver a practical way to both assess and communicate about sustainability-related factors in aquafoods. By clarifying how existing data

sources will support the indicators, we have been able to better understand how this will not only strengthen the framework's applicability, but also highlight areas where data gaps or integration challenges may exist.

As part of this evaluation and reflection stage, we have also considered other similar approaches towards defining relevant indicators for sustainability purposes. For example Grati et al.¹⁰², describe an assessment framework for fisheries focusing on the ecological sustainability of wild-caught aquafood products in Europe. This framework focused on three key impact categories; seabed habitat impact, stock status and bycatch risk of sensitive species. Through the provision of a rating scale from 1 to 5, the respective risks can be effectively communicated. Another prominent piece of work in the US which is similar to ours, is Seafood Watch¹⁰³, a program created by the Monterey Bay Aquarium. Its aim is to promote sustainable seafood choices among consumers, businesses, and policymakers. SeafoodWatch classifies seafood into three categories based on sustainability assessments: (a) Best Choices: Seafood from well-managed, sustainable fisheries and farms with minimal environmental impact, (b) Good Alternatives: Seafood that is acceptable to consume, but with some concerns about fishing practices or environmental impact, and (c) Avoid: Seafood produced in ways that harm marine environments or involve unsustainable practices. The sustainability assessment is carried out in terms of the targeted fish species, the fishing or farming method, the location (e.g. harvested or farmed), and other related sustainability concerns (i.e. bycatch levels, habitat damage, overfishing status, etc.). On reflection of our work to these different programs, we consider that VeriFish has a wider perspective both in terms of the sustainability dimensions (i.e. with the inclusion of Nutrition and Health, as well as social and economic aspects), and we have 'widened the net' of the different data sources that will be exploited in the assessments of the different foods.

Overall, this deliverable further establishes the methodological basis for operationalizing the assessments of products in the aquafood sector, by consolidating the disparate indicators and the data sources that can contribute to their evaluation. The feasibility of this development is demonstrated through the interim version of the VeriFish Knowledge Base (delivered in the same period as D2.4 VeriFish Knowledge Base - interim version), which already integrates and exposes information from some of the described data sources. Furthermore, this work will be utilized in subsequent steps (e.g. for the design and development of the Scoring System).

¹⁰² Grati, F., Druon, J.N., Gascuel, D., Absil, C., Bastardie, F., Bonanomi, S., Fabi, G., Glemarec, G., Guitton, J., Hornborg, S. and Iriondo, A., 2025. Fisheries performance indicators for assessing the ecological sustainability of wild-caught seafood products in Europe. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, p.100632.

¹⁰³ <https://www.seafoodwatch.org/>